

Oribatid mites of Madagascar (Acari: Oribatida)

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„Dedicated to our family members from whom we inherited our restless blood, who had been living with Indians, sailing and possibly even been pirating in the Far East in earlier centuries, or searching the new and the unknown at home, may it be the world exhibition in Paris or a furniture factory in Budapest. But above all, we dedicate our book to Count Móricz Benyovszky, who was probably the first Hungarian to reach Madagascar, became the ruler and master of it, and worked for this land and people.” (Sándor Mahunka)

Abstract. Around 350 Oribatid mite species are listed from Madagascar, with their synonyms and distribution data. New records are provided for 29 species from which three species are new to the fauna of Madagascar: *Acrotrititia reticulata* (Mahunka, 1988), *Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) cf. monodactylus* (Michael, 1888) and *Parasuctobelba subcomplexa* (Balogh & Mahunka, 1968). *Notophthiracarus puylaerti* Niedbala, 2001 is excluded from the fauna of Madagascar due to erroneous citation.

Keywords. Madagascar hotspot, monograph, checklist, fauna list, endemism, species richness

INTRODUCTION

Madagascar is the fourth-largest island in the world and at the same time it is one of the 35 biodiversity hotspots of the world (Myers *et al.* 2000). Its species richness and the high level of endemism is a result of the islands biogeographical history (Vences *et al.* 2009). Acarological interest turned to Madagascar dominantly concerning parasitic and commensal mites of vertebrates (for details see O’Connor 2003). However, the first oribatid mites from the island have been described by János Balogh very early, in the 60’s (Balogh 1960, 1962). His disciple, the also world renown specialist, Sándor Mahunka continued the study of Malagasy oribatid fauna (*e.g.* Mahunka, 1983a, 1993a, 1994 *etc.*).

Based on large collecting activities [*e.g.* by Tamás Pócs (bryologist) and Csaba Csuzdi (earth-

worm specialist) from the Hungarian Natural History Museum, and researchers of the Museum d’Histoire Naturelle Geneva, Switzerland (Dr. B. Hauser and Dr. C. Lienhard)], the study of Madagascar’s Oribatida fauna considerably accelerated from the 80’s but mostly from 90’s. As the number of oribatid species described or recorded grew higher and higher (outlined in Mahunka 2001), the first survey of Oribatid mites of Madagascar was written in 2002 (Mahunka 2002b). In that paper he gave a species list of all known species, completed with literature references. Mahunka’s aim at that time was to give a good survey and basis for future research focusing on the group.

During the following decade taxonomic work on Malagasy Oribatida became more and more intensive (see papers of Mahunka, Fernandez, Ermilov, Niedbala) so Mahunka intended to write

a comprehensive monograph (as already proposed e.g. in Mahunka 2009b, 2010a, Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011). Sadly, preparation of this monograph was demolished by the death of Luise Mahunka-Papp in 2011 and Sándor Mahunka in 2012. Originally it should have been published as a new volume of the *Pedozoologica Hungarica* series. By the end of 2012 the colophon, table of contents, species list and list of localities (as the Material and Methods chapter) has already been written as a cooperation of the couple. After their death, we did not want this huge work to remain unpublished. Based on the notes originally written by Sándor Mahunka and Luise Mahunka-Papp here we present a shorter monograph than originally intended. Such a really deep, comprehensive monograph which resembles Mahunka's first intention was published in 2017 by Niedbała (dedicated to Sándor Mahunka), but not on the whole order Oribatida, "just" on ptyctimous mites (Niedbała 2017).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

From personal communication with Sándor Mahunka and Luise Mahunka-Papp and from their notes which were left behind we know that they wanted to publish not only an up-to-date species list including synonyms and literature references but they wanted to supply it with illustrated redescriptions and distribution data for all species. As such a work is beyond our abilities, we decided to represent a slightly re-edited version, with only an updated species list supplied with synonym lists and distribution data.

Classification is based on the world catalogue by Subias (2004–2022). Although some authors do not exclusively follow Subias' classification, here we follow him because his world catalogue is the mainstay for acarologists dealing with Oribatida in the world. The only exceptions are ptyctimous mites, where we follow Niedbała (Niedbała 2017). Synonym lists contain the descriptive paper and all citations from Madagascar in timeline. We list them without critics or any taxonomic action, just willing to sum all information. In

case the last Madagascar citation uses an old version of the name we end the synonym list with the current name used by Subias (with the year where it was first mentioned in the current form).

Distribution data are given on large scale, also based on Subias (2004–2022) supplied with other literature data only if needed. The list of localities is limited to Madagascar and it contains all locality data supplied with literature references where they were published (in the form as they were published, *i.e.* we did not introduce uniformed names).

For some species we found non-published material in the Soil Zoology Collections of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, too, all identified by Sándor Mahunka. These data are represented here as new records.

List of Oribatid mites of Madagascar

PALAEOSOMATA Grandjean, 1969

CTENACARIDAE Grandjean, 1954

Beklemishevia Zachvatkin, 1945

Beklemishevia demeteri Mahunka, 1984

Beklemishevia demeteri Mahunka, 1984: 88, figs. 1A–G.

Beklemishevia cf. demeteri: Mahunka 1997a: 120.

Beklemishevia cf. demeteri: Mahunka 2002b: 6.

Beklemishevia cf. demeteri: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Localities in Madagascar. 53 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a); Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

APHELACARIDAE Grandjean, 1954

Aphelacarus Grandjean, 1932

Aphelacarus acarinus (Berlese, 1910)

Parhypochthonius acarinus Berlese, 1910a: 219, pl. 19: 42.

Aphelacarinus acarinus: Grandjean 1954: 226, figs 11–17.

Aphelacarus acarinus: Mahunka 1994: 48.

Aphelacarus acarinus: Mahunka 1997a: 117.

Aphelacarus acarinus: Mahunka 2002b: 7.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan (Holarctis, Ethiopis & Nearctis).

Locality in Madagascar. 53 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a).

HYPOCHTHONIOIDEA Berlese, 1910

HYPOCHTHONIIDAE Berlese, 1910

***Eohypochthonius* (*Eohypochthonius*) Jacot, 1938**

***Eohypochthonius* (*Eohypochthonius*) *robustus* Mahunka, 2011**

Eohypochthonius robustus Mahunka, 2011b: 44, figs 1a–d.

Eohypochthonius (*Eohypochthonius*) *robustus*: Subías 2021: 21.

Distribution. Ethiopian region (Madagascar and Mozambique).

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana (Mahunka 2011b).

New records. Prov. Antsiranana [formerly Diego Suarez] Sub-Pref Antsiranana: National Park "Montagne Amber" (= Ambohitra), drive to the "Petit Lac" primary forest soil sampling in the angles by the foothills of a large dead tree. 1090 m, 24.11.1989, leg. B. Hauser (Mad-89/19), Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29.07.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

***Malacoangelia* Berlese, 1913**

***Malacoangelia remigera* Berlese, 1913**

Malacoangelia remigera Berlese, 1913: 101, pl. 7: 86, pl. 8: 88.

Malacoangelia remigera: Mahunka 1997a: 121, fig.4.

Malacoangelia remigera: Mahunka 2002b: 7.

Distribution. Pantropical and subtropical.
Locality in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

ENIOCHTHONIIDAE Grandjean, 1947

***Hypochthoniella* Berlese, 1910**

***Hypochthoniella sumatrana* Mahunka, 1989**

Hypochthoniella sumatrana Mahunka, 1989: 675, figs 1–4.

Hypochthoniella sumatrana: Mahunka 1993: 290.

Hypochthoniella sumatrana: Mahunka 2002b: 7.

Eniochthonius sumatranus: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Hypochthoniella sumatrana: Subías 2022: 32.

Distribution. Oriental and Malgache region.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1993); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

New records. Ambohitantely Forest Reserve E of Manonkazo village (Ankasabz town). Relic xerophyllous (dry evergreen) plateau forest at 1500–1530 m alt. 18°09'23"S, 47°7'02"E. 05–06.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9444) (Afr 857). Toamasina Province. Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park and the Antananarivo Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Afr-923) [2 vials from the same locality, with the same labels]; (Prov. Tamatave), Sub-pref. Moramanga): Analamazoatra Special Reserve (formerly Perinet) near Andasibe, primary forest, soil sample from the foot of a *Ravensara* sp. tree (Lauraceae), 1020 m, extracted with Berlese funnel, 21.11. 1989, leg. B. Hauser (Mad-89/3).

LOHMANNIDAE Berlese, 1916

***Dendracarus* Balogh, 1961**

***Dendracarus pulchellus* Balogh, 1960**

Dendracarus pulchellus Balogh, 1960: 16, figs 13–14.

Dendracarus pulchellus: Balogh 1961: 30, figs 35–36.
Dendracarus pulchellus: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 346, pl. 34: A–B.
Dendracarus pulchellus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Dendracarus pulchellus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 74, pl. 128: 9–10.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1960).

***Javacarus* Balogh, 1961**

***Javacarus porosus* Hammer, 1979**

Javacarus porosus Hammer, 1979: 9, fig. 8.
Javacarus porosus: Mahunka 1993: 291, figs 1–4.
Javacarus porosus: Mahunka 1997a: 118.
Javacarus porosus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Distribution. Pantropical except Australia.

Localities in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993, Mahunka 1997a).

***Meristacarus* Grandjean, 1934**

***Meristacarus madagascarensis* Balogh, 1961**

Meristacarus madagascarensis Balogh, 1961: 28, figs 23–24.
Meristacarus madagascarensis: Balogh 1962a: 122, figs 1–3.
Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 340, pl. 23: B.
Meristacarus madagascarensis: Mahunka 1997a: 118.
Meristacarus madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Meristacarus madagascarensis madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 69, pl. 122: 2.

Distribution. Ethiopian region (Madagascar) and Oriental region (Thailand and Vietnam).

Localities in Madagascar. Nosy Be, Pointe a la Fievre (Balogh 1962a); Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

***Paulianacarus* (*Millotacarus*) Balogh, 1961**

***Paulianacarus* (*Millotacarus*) *granulatus* (Balogh, 1960)**

Millotacarus granulatus Balogh, 1960: 12, figs 10–12.
Millotacarus granulatus: Balogh 1961a: 29, figs 31–32.
Millotacarus granulatus: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 344, pl. 31, figs A–B.
Millotacarus granulatus: Coetzee 2001: 65.
Millotacarus granulatus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Millotacarus granulatus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 72, pl. 126, fig. 7.
Paulianacarus (*Millotacarus*) *granulatus*: Subías 2004: 41.

Distribution. Madagascar and India (Andhra Pradesh).

Locality in Madagascar. Maroansetra, Ambo-divoangy (Balogh 1960).

***Paulianacarus* (*Paulianacarus*) Balogh, 1961**

***Paulianacarus* (*Paulianacarus*) *laevis* Balogh, 1960**

Paulianacarus laevis Balogh, 1960: 10, figs 3–4.
Paulianacarus levis (sic!): Balogh 1961: 29, figs 25–26.
Paulianacarus levis (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 1987: 344, pl. 31: C.
Paulianacarus laevis: Coetzee 2001: 64.
Paulianacarus laevis: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Paulianacarus levis (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 72, pl. 127: 5.
Paulianacarus laevis: Subías 2004: 40.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankaratra, Man jakatomso (Balogh 1960).

***Paulianacarus* (*Paulianacarus*) *nodosus* Balogh, 1961**

Paulianacarus nodosus Balogh, 1960: 10, figs 5–7.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Balogh 1961: 29, figs 27–28.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 344, pl. 30: B–C.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Coetzee 2001: 64.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 72, pl. 127: 3–4.
Paulianacarus nodosus: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Maroantsetra, Am-bodivoangy (Balogh 1960); Andasibe (Perinet) (Mahunka 2011b).

New record. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rain-forest on the W slope at 1-300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859)

Paulianacarus (Paulianacarus) rugosus
Balogh, 1960

Paulianacarus rugosus Balogh, 1960: 12, figs 8–9.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Balogh 1961: 29, figs 29–30.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Balogh & Balogh 1987: 344, pl. 29: D.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Mahunka 1997a: 118.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Coetzee 2001: 64.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Paulianacarus rugosus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 72, pl. 127: 2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Italaviana, Fano-vana (Balogh 1960); Analamazoatra Special Reserve, Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a).

New record. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

MESOPLOPHORIDAE Ewing, 1917

***Archoplophora* Hammen, 1959**

***Archoplophora rostralis* (Willmann, 1930)**

Phthiracarulus rostralis Willmann, 1930: 245, figs 8–9.
Archoplophora rostralis: Niedbala 2017: 13, fig. 4.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankarafantsika National Park (Niedbala 2017)

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) Berlese, 1904

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) Africana
Balogh, 1958

Mesoplophora africana Balogh, 1958: 32.
Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) africana: Niedbala 2017: 13, fig. 5.

Distribution. Afrotropical, central and eastern parts (Niedbala 2017).

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Zombitse National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) invisitata
Niedbala, 1983

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) invisitata Niedbala, 1983b: 647, figs 1–11.
Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) invisitata: Niedbala 2017: 16, fig. 6.

Distribution. Pantropical, Oriental and Afrotropical Regions (Niedbala 2017).

Locality in Madagascar. Ankarafantsika National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) similis
Mahunka, 2011

Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) similis Mahunka, 2011b: 46, figs 2a–d.
Mesoplophora (Mesoplophora) similis: Niedbala 2017: 16, fig. 7.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 2011b).

Mesoplophora (Parplophora) Niedbala, 1985

Mesoplophora (Parplophora) madegassica
Mahunka, 2009

Mesoplophora (Parplophora) madegassica Mahunka, 2009c: 340, figs 1–4.
Mesoplophora (Parplophora) madegassica: Niedbala 2017: 19, fig. 9.
Mesoplophora (Parplophora) madegassica: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 442.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

PROTOPLOPHOROIDEA Ewing, 1917

COSMOCHTHONIIDAE Grandjean, 1947

Cosmochthonius (Cosmochthonius) Berlese, 1910

***Cosmochthonius (Cosmochthonius) margaritatus* Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011**

Cosmochthonius margaritatus Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 126, figs 1a–f.

Cosmochthonius (Cosmochthonius) margaritatus: Subías 2014: 27.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. On the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

***Cosmochthonius (Cosmochthonius) semiareolatus* Hammer, 1966**

Cosmochthonius semiareolatus Hammer, 1966: 14, pl. 3, fig. 12.

Cosmochthonius (Cosmochthonius) semiareolatus: Subías 2004: 33.

Cosmochthonius semiareolatus: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011: 128, figs 2a–d.

Distribution. New Zealand, Madagascar and Argentina.

Locality in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011). However, this locality data may be doubtful. For details see the *Remarks*.

Remarks. During collection research we found the label in the vial referring to a different locality than the published: Toamasina Province, Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park and the Antananarivo Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.

1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Afr-923). Even in the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka this locality is connected to the species.

SPHAEROCHTHONIIDAE Grandjean, 1947

***Sphaerochthonius* Berlese, 1910**

***Sphaerochthonius variesetosus* Mahunka, 1997**

Sphaerochthonius variesetosus Mahunka, 1997a: 121, figs 1–4.

Sphaerochthonius variosetosus (sic!): Mahunka 2002b: 7.

Sphaerochthonius variesetosus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 53, pl. 103, fig. 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

New record. Toamasina Province. Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park and the Antananarivo Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Af-923).

PROTOPLOPHORIDAE Ewing, 1917

***Bursoplophora* Subías & Pérez-Iñigo, 1978**

***Bursoplophora madagassica* Mahunka, 1994**

Bursoplophora madagassica Mahunka, 1994: 49, figs 1–7.

Bursoplophora madagassica: Mahunka 2002b: 7.

Bursoplophora madagassica: Niedbała 2004b: 820, figs 7. D–J.

Bursoplophora madagassica: Niedbała 2017: 10, fig. 2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary, 53 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1994).

Prototritia Berlese, 1916

***Prototritia armadillo* (Berlese, 1916)**

Arthrhoplophora (Prototritia) armadillo Berlese, 1916: 66.

Prototritia armadillo: Niedbała 2017: 11, fig. 3.

Distribution. Africa, eastern part.

Localities in Madagascar: Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbała 2017).

EPILOHMANNIOIDEA Oudemans, 1923

EPILOHMANNIIDAE Oudemans, 1923

Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) Berlese, 1916

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) insignipes*
Balogh, 1962**

Epilohmannia insignipes Balogh, 1962a: 123, figs 4–6.

Epilohmannia insignipes: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Epilohmannia insignipes: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 56, pl. 106, figs 3–4.

Epilohmannia insignipes: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Epilohmannia insignipes: Subías 2017: 50.

Distribution. Ethiopian region (Guinea Ecua-torial: Isl. Bioko [Fernando Poo] and Kenya).

Localities in Madagascar: Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

***Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) minuta*
Berlese, 1920**

Epilohmannia minuta Berlese, 1920: 149.

Epilohmannia pallida: Mahunka 2009c: 338.

Epilohmannia (Epilohmannia) minuta: Subías 2017: 50.

Epilohmannia minuta: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 442.

Distribution. Tropical (Ethiopian, Oriental: India and Thailand, and Neotropical) central and eastern U.S.A.

Locality in Madagascar: Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

EUPHTHRACAROIDEA JACOT, 1930

EUPHTHRACARIDAE JACOT, 1930

Acrotrititia Jacot, 1923

***Acrotrititia ardua* (C. L. Koch, 1841)**

Hoplophora ardua C. L. Koch, 1841: 32, 15.

Rhysotrititia ardua: Niedbała 2001: 87.

Rhysotrititia ardua: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Rhysotrititia ardua: Niedbała 2004a: 334.

Acrotrititia ardua: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 588.

Acrotrititia ardua: Niedbała 2017: 44, fig. 27.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar: Befingotra (Niedbała 2001); Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais, North of Manankazo village, Ranomafana National Park, Zombitse National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Acrotrititia divida* (Mahunka, 1991)**

Rhysotrititia divida Mahunka, 1991: 344, figs 51–55.

Acrotrititia divida: Niedbała 2017: 48, fig. 28.

Distribution. Pantropical (eastern part) (Niedbała 2017).

Locality in Madagascar: Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Acrotrititia granulata* (Mahunka, 1999)**

Rhysotrititia granulata Mahunka, 1999b: 81, figs 18–20.

Rhysotrititia granulata: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Rhysotrititia granulata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 46.

Rhysotrititia granulata: Niedbała 2004a: 334.

Acrotrititia granulata: Niedbała 2017: 48, fig. 34D.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: between Ambatolona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała 2017).

***Acrotrititia paraardua* Niedbała & Starý, 2015**

Acrotritia paraardua Niedbala & Starý, 2015c: 1692, fig. 2.

Acrotritia paraardua: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Acrotritia paraardua: Niedbala 2017: 48, fig. 29.

Acrotritia paraardua: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 442.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala & Starý 2015c, Niedbala 2017); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Acrotritia paradikra Niedbala & Starý, 2015

Acrotritia paradikra Niedbala & Starý, 2015c: 1695, fig. 3.

Acrotritia paradikra: Niedbala 2017: 51, fig. 30.

Distribution. Madagascar, Brasil and Mexico.

Localities in Madagascar: Ankarafantsika National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2015c); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Acrotritia refracta (Niedbala, 1998)

Rhysotritia refracta Niedbala, 1998b: 479, figs 155–159.

Acrotritia refracta: Niedbala 2017: 51, fig. 31.

Distribution. Pantropical.

Localities in Madagascar: Andasibe National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Acrotritia reticulata (Mahunka, 1988)

Rhysotritia reticulata Mahunka, 1988a: 358, figs 32–34.

Acrotritia reticulata: Subías 2004: 46.

Distribution. Tanzania, Canada, Argentina.

New record. National Park Montagne d'Ambre, Lac Maudit, leg. R. Schabetsberger.

Remarks. This species is new to the fauna of Madagascar.

Acrotritia rustica (Niedbala, 1991)

Rhysotritia rustica Niedbala, 1991: 34, figs 8–14.

Rhysotritia rustica: Niedbala 2001: 88.

Rhysotritia rustica: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Rhysotritia rustica: Niedbala 2004a: 334.

Acrotritia rustica: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Acrotritia rustica: Niedbala 2017: 51, fig. 32.

Acrotritia rustica: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Pantropical (Australian: Australia and New Guinea) and Holarctic: Southern Palearctic (Turkey and Eastern Palearctic) and South-eastern U.S.A.

Localities in Madagascar: Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017).

Acrotritia spiculifera (Mahunka, 1991)

Rhysotritia clavata spiculifera Mahunka, 1991: 344, figs 43–50.

Rhysotritia spiculifera: Mahunka 1999b: 81.

Rhysotritia spiculifera: Niedbala 2001: 88.

Rhysotritia spiculifera: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Rhysotritia spiculifera: Niedbala 2004a: 334.

Acrotritia spiculifera: Niedbala 2017: 55, fig. 33.

Distribution. Pantropical (except Neotropical) and subtropical.

Localities in Madagascar: Between Ambatolona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Andasibe National Park, Beforona commune Ambatondralanga (Niedbala 2017).

Acrotritia vestita (Berlese, 1913)

Hoplogruberia vestita Berlese, 1913: 103, figs: 8: 103, 130a.

Rhysotritia anchistea: Niedbala 1998a: 468, figs 112–116.

Rhysotritia cf. anchistea: Mahunka 1999b: 78.

Rhysotritia cf. anchistea: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Rhysotritia comteae Mahunka, 1983: 273, figs 4–7.

Rhysotritia comteae: Niedbala 2001: 87.

Rhysotritia comtae (sic!): Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Rhysotritia comteae: Niedbala 2004a: 334.

Acrotritia comteae: Niedbala 2008: 3.

Acrotritia vestita: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Acarotritia vestita: Niedbala 2017: 55, fig. 34.

Distribution. Pantropical (frequent), Eastern Palearctic and Eastern Canada.

Localities in Madagascar. Between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b *Rhysotritia cf. anchistea*); Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001, Niedbala 2008 *Rhysotritia comteae*); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala & Starý 2016a *Acrotritia vestita*); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune Ambatondralanga, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d’Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017 *Acrotritia vestita*).

New record. National Park Montagne d’Ambre, Lac Maudit, leg. R. Schabetsberger.

***Bukitritia* Mahunka, 1990**

Bukitritia timah Mahunka, 1990

Bukitritia timah Mahunka, 1990a: 69, figs 14–21.

Bukitritia timah: Mahunka 1999b: 73.

Bukitritia timah: Niedbala 2001: 89.

Bukitritia timah: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Bukitritia timah: Niedbala 2004a: 334.

Bukitritia timah: Niedbala 2017: 58, fig. 35.

Distribution. Malaysia and Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b).

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) Ewing, 1917

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) duplex
Niedbala & Starý, 2014

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) duplex Niedbala & Starý, 2014c: 486, figs 1A–G.

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) duplex: Niedbala 2017: 41, fig. 23.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Beforona commune, Vohidrazana (Niedbala & Starý 2014c, Niedbala 2017).

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) incredibilis (Mahunka, 1999)

Niedbalaia incredibilis Mahunka, 1999b: 77, figs 12–17.

Euphthiracarus incredibilis: Niedbala 2001: 86, figs 656–658.

Niedbalaia incredibilis: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Niedbalaia incredibilis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 45.

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) incredibilis: Niedbala 2004a: 334.

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) incredibilis: Niedbala 2017: 41, fig. 24.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b).

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) netron Niedbala & Starý, 2014

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) netron Niedbala & Starý, 2014c: 486, figs 2A–E.

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) netron: Niedbala 2017: 44, fig. 25.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park, Vatoharanana (Niedbala & Starý 2014c, Niedbala 2017).

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) paranetron Niedbala & Starý, 2016

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) paranetron Niedbala & Starý, 2016b: 486, fig. 2.

Euphthiracarus (Euphthiracarus) paranetron: Niedbala 2017: 44, fig. 26.

Euphthiracarus paranetron: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016b, Niedbala 2017).

Microtritia Märkel, 1964

***Microtritia hauseri* Mahunka, 1993**

Microtritia hauseri Mahunka, 1993a: 293, figs 11–14.
Microtritia hauseri: Niedbala 1998a: 67, figs 146–148.
Microtritia hauseri: Mahunka 1999b: 73.
Microtritia hauseri: Niedbala 2001: 89.
Microtritia hauseri: Mahunka 2002b: 8.
Microtritia hauseri: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 46, pl. 96, figs 4–6.
Microtritia hauseri: Niedbala 2004a: 334.
Microtritia hauseri: Mahunka 2010a: 48.
Microtritia hauseri: Niedbala 2017: 58, fig. 36.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve before Andasibe (Mahunka 1993a, Niedbala 1998a); between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park, Ambatondralanga, Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Beforona commune (Niedbala 2017).

New record. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W slope at 1–300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859).

***Microtritia striatissima* Mahunka, 1999**

Microtritia striatissima Mahunka, 1999b: 74, figs 8–11.
Microtritia striatissima: Niedbala 2001: 89, figs 660–661.
Microtritia striatissima: Mahunka 2002b: 8.
Microtritia striatissima: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 45.
Microtritia striatissima: Niedbala 2004a: 334.
Microtritia striatissima: Niedbala 2017: 61, fig. 37.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Beforona commune, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

***Microtritia tropica* Märkel, 1964**

Microtritia tropica Märkel, 1964: 49, fig. 11a–c.
Microtritia tropica: Niedbala 2008: 3.
Microtritia tropica: Mahunka 2009c: 338.
Microtritia tropica: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.
Microtritia tropica: Niedbala 2017: 61, fig. 38.
Microtritia tropica: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Pantropical and Japan.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2008); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, North of Manankazo village, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017).

ORIBOTRITIIDAE Grandjean, 1954

Indotritia (Indotritia) Jacot, 1929

***Indotritia (Indotritia) javensis* (Sellnick, 1923)**

Tritia javensis Sellnick, 1923: 14, figs 3, 14, 26.
Indotritia (Indotritia) javensis: Subías: 2004: 43.
Indotritia javensis: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 588.
Indotritia javensis: Niedbala 2017: 35, fig. 19.

Distribution. Pantropical species introduced to southern and eastern parts of Palaearctic (Niedbala 2017).

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne de Français (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune, Montagne de Français, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

***Indotritia (Indotritia) paulyi* Niedbala, 1998**

Indotritia (Indotritia) paulyi Niedbala, 1998a: 41, figs 52–57.
Indotritia paulyi: Mahunka 1999b: 69.
Indotritia (Indotritia) paulyi: Niedbala 2001: 85.

Indotritia paulyi: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Indotritia paulyi: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 44, pl. 91, figs 7–9.
Indotritia (Indotritia) paulyi: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Indotritia (Indotritia) paulyi: Niedbała 2017: 38, fig. 21.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Foulpointe (Niedbała 1998a); between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Befingotra, Fianarantsoa (Niedbała 2001); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Indotritia (Indotritia) tripartita* Niedbała, 1998**

Indotritia (Indotritia) tripartita Niedbała, 1998: 44, figs 58–63.
Indotritia (Indotritia) tripartita: Niedbała 2017: 38, fig. 22.

Distribution. Afrotropical.

Localities in Madagascar: Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) Jacot, 1924

***Oribotritia (Oribotritia) breviseta*
Niedbała & Starý, 2015**

Oribotritia breviseta Niedbała & Starý, 2015c: 1690, fig. 1.
Oribotritia breviseta: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 588.
Oribotritia breviseta: Niedbała 2017: 22, fig. 10.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) breviseta: Subías 2020: 51.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Andasibe National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2015c); Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbała 2017).

***Oribotritia (Oribotritia) mahunkai*
Niedbała & Starý, 2013**

Oribotritia mahunkai Niedbała & Starý, 2013: 338, figs 1A–F.
Oribotritia mahunkai: Niedbała 2017: 24, fig. 11.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) mahunkai: Subías 2020: 52.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała & Starý 2013, Niedbała 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais, North of Manankazo village, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Oribotritia (Oribotritia) paraspinosa*
Mahunka, 1999**

Oribotritia paraspinosa Mahunka, 1999b: 70, figs 1–5.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Niedbała 2001: 82, figs 646–650.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Niedbała 2008: 3.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 588.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Niedbała 2017: 24, fig. 12.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) paraspinosa: Subías 2020: 52.
Oribotritia paraspinosa: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 442.

Distribution. Eastern islands of the Afrotropical Region (Niedbała 2017).

Localities in Madagascar: Between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Befingotra, Fianarantsoa (Niedbała 2001); Fianarantsoa, 28 km SSW Ambositra, (Niedbała 2008); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Beforona commune, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Oribotritia (Oribotritia) perpusilla* Niedbała & Starý, 2016**

Oribotritia perpusilla Niedbała & Starý, 2016b: 486, fig. 1.

Oribotritia perpusilla: Niedbała 2017: 24, fig. 13.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) perpusilla: Subías 2020: 52.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016b, Niedbała 2017).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) spinosa
(Mahunka, 1988)

Philotritia spinosa Mahunka, 1988b: 1098, figs 38–44.
Oribotritia spinosa: Niedbała 1998a: 23, figs 11–17.
Oribotritia spinosa: Mahunka 1999b: 73, figs 6–7.
Oribotritia spinosa: Niedbała 2001: 91.
Oribotritia spinosa: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Oribotritia spinosa: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 42, pl. 86, figs 1–3.
Oribotritia spinosa: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Oribotritia spinosa: Niedbała 2008: 3.
Oribotritia spinosa: Niedbała 2017: 28, fig. 14.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) spinosa: Subías 2020: 53.

Distribution. Madagascar, Mauritius and Reunion.

Localities in Madagascar: Foulpointe, Pont Onibé, Vavateze (Niedbała 1998a); Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park, between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999b); Fianarantsoa (Niedbała 2008); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Beforona commune, Montagne de Francais, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) striata Mahunka, 2009

Oribotritia striata Mahunka, 2009a: 93, figs 6–9.
Oribotritia striata: Niedbała 2017: 28, fig. 15.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) striata: Subías 2020: 53.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbała 2017).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) succincta Niedbała, 1998

Oribotritia succincta Niedbała, 1998: 25, figs 18–22.
Oribotritia succincta: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Oribotritia succincta: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 42, pl. 85, figs 10–12.
Oribotritia succincta: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Oribotritia succincta: Niedbała 2017: 31, fig. 16.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) succincta: Subías 2020: 53.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Fuolpointe, Vavateze (Niedbała, 1998).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) tiwi Mahunka, 1987

Oribotritia tiwi Mahunka, 1987: 83, figs 27–30.
Oribotritia tiwi: Niedbała 1998a: 28, figs 23–27.
Oribotritia tiwi: Niedbała 2001: 84.
Oribotritia tiwi: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Oribotritia tiwi: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Oribotritia tiwi: Niedbała 2017: 31, fig. 17.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) tiwi: Subías 2020: 53.

Distribution. Afrotropical, eastern part (Niedbała 2017).

Localities in Madagascar: Foulpointe (Niedbała 1998a); Befingotra, Fianarantsoa (Niedbała 2001).

Oribotritia (Oribotritia) virgulata Niedbała, 2001

Oribotritia virgulata Niedbała, 2001: 84, figs 651–655.
Oribotritia virgulata: Mahunka 2002b: 9.
Oribotritia virgulata: Niedbała 2004a: 334.
Oribotritia virgulata: Niedbała 2008: 3.
Oribotritia virgulata: Niedbała 2017: 31, fig. 18.
Oribotritia (Oribotritia) virgulata: Subías 2020: 53.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Befingotra (Niedbała 2001); Fianarantsoa (Niedbała 2008); Andasibe National Park, Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała 2017).

PHTHIRACAROIDEA Petry, 1841

PHTHIRACARIDAE Perty, 1841

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) Ewing, 1917

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) primus
Niedbała & Starý, 2015

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) primus Niedbała & Starý, 2015a: 46, figs 32–41.

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) primus: Niedbała 2017 169, fig. 115.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2015a, Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) striculus
(C. L. Koch, 1836)

Hoplophora stricula C. L. Koch, 1836: 2, 10.

Atropacarus (Atropacarus) striculus: Niedbała 2017: 169, fig. 116.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) Berlese, 1923

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei
(Balogh, 1958)

Steganacarus andrei Balogh, 1958: 33.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) andrei: Niedbała 2017: 141, fig. 96.

Distribution. Pantropical.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) balazsi
(Mahunka, 1983)

Hoplophorella balazsi Mahunka, 1983a: 99, figs 1–4.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) balazsi: Niedbała 2001: 58, figs 492–495.

Hoplophorella balazsi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Kakophthiracarus balazsi: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 22, pl. 35, figs 3–5.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) balazsi: Niedbała 2004a: 333.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) balazsi: Niedbała 2017: 144, fig. 97.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Is. Nosy Be, (Mahunka 1983a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) cucullatus
(Ewing, 1909)

Hoplophorella cucullata Ewing, 1909: 133, fig. 35.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) cucullatus: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 590.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) cucullatus: Niedbała 2017: 144, fig. 98.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne de Français (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ankarafantsika National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) distinctus
Niedbała & Starý, 2014

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) distinctus Niedbała & Starý, 2014b: 75, figs 2A–J.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) distinctus: Niedbała 2017: 147, fig. 99.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała & Starý 2014b, Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) hamatus
(Ewing, 1909)

Hoplophorella hamatum Ewing, 1909: 134, fig. 36.

Hoplophorella hamata: Mahunka 2009c: 340.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) hamatus: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 590.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) hamatus: Niedbała 2017: 147, fig. 100.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar. 73 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 2009c); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Montagne de Français (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ankarafantsika National Park, (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lemurius
(Mahunka, 1993)

Hoplophorella lemuria Mahunka, 1993a: 293, figs 5–10.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lemurius: Niedbała 2001: 61, figs 536–538.

Hoplophorella lemuria: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Hoplophorella lemuria: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 23, pl. 37, figs 9–10.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lemurius: Niedbała 2004a: 333.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) lemurius: Niedbała 2017: 147, fig. 101A.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1993a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) mahunkai
Niedbała & Starý, 2013

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) mahunkai Niedbała & Starý, 2013: 342, figs 3A–F.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) mahunkai: Niedbała 2017: 151, figs 101B–G, 102.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) othneios Niedbała & Starý, 2014b: 78, figs 3A–G, 4A–E.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) othneios: Niedbała 2017: 151.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2013 *mahunkai*, Niedbała 2017 *mahunkai*), Ambohitantely Special Reserve; Ranomafana National (Niedbała & Starý 2014b *othneios*).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) oblongus
Niedbała, 1983

Hoplophorella oblonga Niedbała, 1983a: 131, figs 18–32.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) oblongus: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 590.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) oblongus: Niedbała 2017: 154, fig. 107.

Distribution. Afrotropical, central and eastern parts.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ankarafantsika National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) paralemurius
Niedbała & Starý, 2016

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) paralemurius Niedbała & Starý, 2016a: 595, figs 3A–K.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) paralemurius: Niedbała 2017: 159, fig. 108.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) paralemurius: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Montagne d’Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) parastenos
Niedbała & Starý, 2016

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) parastenos Niedbała & Starý, 2016b: 494, fig. 6.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) parastenos Niedbała 2017: 159, fig. 109.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d’Ambre National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016b, Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) stilifer
(Hammer, 1961)

Steganacarus stilifer Hammer, 1961: 132, fig. 132.

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) stilifer: Niedbała 2017: 162, fig. 111.

Distribution. Pantropical.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) vitrinus
(Berlese, 1913)

Hoplophorella vitrinum Berlese, 1913: 103, figs 100a–b.

Hoplophorella vitrina: Mahunka 2009c: 339.
Hoplophorella vitrina: Mahunka 2010a: 48.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) vitrinus: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 590.
Atropacarus (Hoplophorella) vitrinus: Niedbała 2017: 166, figs 113–114.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 2009c); Manongarivo Special Reserve (Mahunka 2010a); Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a); Andranomena Special Reserve, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais, Zombitse National Park, (Niedbała 2017).

***Arphthycarus* Niedbała, 1994**

***Arphthycarus inelegans* (Niedbała, 1986)**

Hoplophthiracarus inelegans Niedbała, 1986: 115, figs 1–7.
Arphthiracarus inelegans: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 589.
Arphthiracarus inelegans: Niedbała 2017: 85, fig. 54.
Arphthiracarus inelegans: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Pantropical.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017); Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbała 2017).

***Arphthycarus phoxos* Niedbała & Starý, 2016**

Arphthiracarus phoxos Niedbała & Starý, 2016: 590, figs 1A–G.
Arphthiracarus phoxos: Niedbała 2017: 88, fig. 56.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017).

***Arphthycarus sculptilis* (Niedbała, 1988)**

Hoplophthiracarus sculptilis Niedbała, 1988: 79, figs 1–8.
Arphthycarus sculptilis: Niedbała 2001: 42, figs 313–318.
Arphthycarus sculptilis: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Arphthycarus sculptilis: Niedbała 2004a: 332.
Arphthycarus sculptilis: Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 589.
Arphthycarus sculptilis: Niedbała 2017: 88, figs 57–58.

Distribution. Madagascar, Comoro Islands, Reunion and Cameroon.

Localities in Madagascar. Foulpointe (Niedbała 2001); Montagne de Francais (Niedbała & Starý 2016a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Andranomena Special Reserve, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbała 2017).

***Arphthycarus veteratorius* (Niedbała, 1988)**

Hoplophthiracarus veteratorius Niedbała, 1988: 81, figs 9–15.
Arphthycarus veteratorius: Niedbała 2017: 92, fig. 60.

Distribution. Afrotropical, eastern islands: Madagascar and Comoros.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Beforona commune, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbała 2017).

***Hoplophthiracarus* Jacot, 1933**

***Hoplophthiracarus paratryssos* Niedbała & Starý, 2015**

Hoplophthiracarus paratryssos Niedbała & Starý, 2015a: 42, figs 9–16.
Hoplophthiracarus paratryssos: Niedbała 2017: 82, fig. 53.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2015a, Niedbała 2017); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbała 2017).

***Notophthiracarus* Ramsay, 1966**

***Notophthiracarus andasibensis* Niedbała & Starý, 2014**

Notophthiracarus andasibensis Niedbała & Starý, 2014a: 80, figs 1A–G.

Notophthiracarus andasibensis: Niedbala 2017: 99, fig. 64.

Notophthiracarus andasibensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2014a); Andasibe National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2014a, Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus bicarinatus Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus bicarinatus Niedbala, 2001: 48, figs 381–387.

Notophthiracarus bicarinatus: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus bicarinatus: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus bicarinatus: Niedbala 2017: 99, fig. 65.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Befingotra (Niedbala 2001).

Notophthiracarus dispersus

Niedbala & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus dispersus Niedbala & Starý, 2015a: 44, figs 25–31.

Notophthiracarus dispersus: Niedbala 2017: 102, fig. 68.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Beforona commune (Niedbala & Starý 2015a, Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus echinus (Balogh, 1962)

Hoplophorella echinus Balogh, 1962a: 146, figs 41–43.

Notophthiracarus (N.) echinus: Mahunka 1990b: 204, figs 15–17.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Niedbala 2001: 49, figs 401–404.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 28, pl. 49, figs 11–13.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Notophthiracarus echinus: Niedbala 2017: 106, fig. 69.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017); Andasibe National Park, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus inusitatus Mahunka, 2010

Notophthiracarus inusitatus Mahunka, 2010a: 50, figs 5–9.

Notophthiracarus inusitatus: Niedbala 2017: 106, figs 70–71.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a); Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus lineatus

Niedbala & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus lineatus Niedbala & Starý, 2015b: 64, fig. 1.

Notophthiracarus lineatus: Niedbala 2017: 110, fig. 72.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2015b, Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus liratus Niedbala & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus liratus Niedbala & Starý, 2015b: 66, fig. 2.

Notophthiracarus liratus: Niedbala 2017: 110, fig. 73.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2015b, Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus malagasensis
(Mahunka, 2010)

Austrophthiracarus aokii malagasensis Mahunka, 2010a: 48, figs 1–4.

Notophthiracarus malagasensis: Niedbała 2017: 110, figs 74–75.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

Remarks. During collection research we found that the label in the vial refers to a different locality than the published one: Antsiranana Prov. Réserve Spéciale de Manongarivo. Tall mesic evergreen forest with huge sandstone cliff and boulders 7.5 km SW of Antanambao village, at the W side of Ambakatra river. At 460–570 m alt. 13°55.5'N, 48°27.3'E, 24.07.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9857) (Afr-918). Even in the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka this locality is connected to the species.

Notophthiracarus medius
Niedbała & Starý, 2016

Notophthiracarus medius Niedbała & Starý, 2016b: 491, fig. 5.

Notophthiracarus medius: Niedbała 2017: 115, fig. 76.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe–Mantadia National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016b, Niedbała 2017).

Notophthiracarus micidus
Niedbała & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus micidus Niedbała & Starý, 2015b: 66, fig. 3.

Notophthiracarus micidus: Niedbała 2017: 115, fig. 77.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park, Zombitse National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2015b, Niedbała 2017); Andasibe-Mantadia

National Park, Beforona commune, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbała 2017).

Notophthiracarus obliquus
Niedbała & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus obliquus Niedbała & Starý, 2015b: 68, fig. 4.

Notophthiracarus obliquus: Niedbała 2017: 118, fig. 78.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2015b, Niedbała 2017).

Notophthiracarus pandanensis
Niedbała & Starý, 2014

Notophthiracarus pandanensis Niedbała & Starý, 2014a: 80, figs 2A–H.

Notophthiracarus pandanensis: Niedbała 2017: 118, fig. 79.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbała & Starý 2014a, Niedbała 2017).

Notophthiracarus parapaulianus
Niedbała & Starý, 2016

Notophthiracarus parapaulianus Niedbała & Starý 2016a: 592, figs 2A–G.

Notophthiracarus parapaulianus: Niedbała 2017: 118, fig. 80.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbała & Starý 2016a, Niedbała 2017).

Notophthiracarus parasomalicus Niedbała, 2001

Notophthiracarus parasomalicus Niedbała, 2001: 50, figs 419–424.

Notophthiracarus parasomalicus: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus parasomalicus: Niedbała 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus parasomalicus: Niedbala 2017: 122, fig. 82.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, Befingotra (Niedbala 2001); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus parasummersi Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus parasummersi Niedbala, 2001: 51, figs 425–430.

Notophthiracarus parasummersi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus parasummersi: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus parasummersi: Niedbala 2017: 125, fig. 83.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus parilloi Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus parilloi Niedbala, 2001: 51, figs 432–437.

Notophthiracarus parilloi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus parilloi: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus parilloi: Niedbala 2017: 125, fig. 84.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Befingotra (Niedbala 2001); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus paulianus (Balogh, 1962)

Hoplophorella pauliani Balogh, 1962a: 148, figs 44–45.

Notophthiracarus (?) paulianus: Niedbala 2001: 52, figs 405–406.

Hoplophorella pauliani: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus pauliani: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 28, pl. 50, figs 1–2.

Notophthiracarus (?) paulianus: Niedbala 2017: 125, fig. 85.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a).

Notophthiracarus procerus Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus procerus Niedbala, 2001: 52, figs 438–443.

Notophthiracarus procerus: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus procerus: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Notophthiracarus procerus: Niedbala 2017: 128, fig. 86.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, Befingotra (Niedbala 2001).

Notophthiracarus pseudosomalicus

Mahunka, 2010

Notophthiracarus pseudosomalicus Mahunka, 2010a: 50, figs 10–17.

Notophthiracarus pseudosomalicus: Niedbala 2017: 128, fig. 87.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

Notophthiracarus quasisimilis

Niedbala & Starý, 2015

Notophthiracarus quasisimilis Niedbala & Starý, 2015b: 70, fig. 5.

Notophthiracarus quasisimilis: Niedbala 2017: 131, fig. 89.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2015b, Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus quasisomalicus

Niedbala & Starý, 2014

Notophthiracarus quasisomalicus Niedbala & Starý, 2014a: 81, figs 3A–H.

Notophthiracarus quasisomalicus: Niedbala 2017: 134, fig. 90.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala & Starý 2014a); Andasibe National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus rafalskii Niedbala, 1997

Notophthiracarus rafalskii Niedbala, 1997: 87, figs 38–44.

Notophthiracarus rafalskii: Niedbala 2001: 53, figs 454–458.

Notophthiracarus rafalskii: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus rafalskii: Niedbala 2004a: 333.

Notophthiracarus rafalskii: Niedbala 2017: 134, fig. 91.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Foulpointe (Niedbala 1997, Niedbala 2001).

Notophthiracarus reticularis
Niedbala & Starý, 2014

Notophthiracarus reticularis Niedbala & Starý, 2014a: 81: Figs 4A–F.

Notophthiracarus reticularis: Niedbala 2017 137, fig. 92.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2014a, Niedbala 2017); Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus similis Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus similis Niedbala, 2001: 54, figs 465–470.

Notophthiracarus similis: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus similis: Niedbala 2004a: 333.

Notophthiracarus similis: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 590.

Notophthiracarus similis: Niedbala 2017: 137, fig. 93.

Notophthiracarus similis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, Befin-goitra (Niedbala 2001); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Andasibe-

Mantadia National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Beforona commune, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017).

Notophthiracarus summersi Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus summersi Niedbala, 2001: 56, figs 471–475.

Notophthiracarus summersi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus summersi: Niedbala 2004a: 333.

Notophthiracarus summersi: Niedbala 2017: 137, fig. 94.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, Befin-goitra (Niedbala 2001).

Notophthiracarus zebra (Balogh, 1962)

Hoplophorella zebra Balogh, 1962a: 144 figs 36–40.

Notophthiracarus zebrus: Niedbala 2001: 56, figs 477–484.

Hoplophorella zebra: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus zebra: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 28, pl. 49, figs 8–10.

Notophthiracarus zebrus: Niedbala 2004a: 333.

Notophthiracarus zebra: Mahunka 2009a: 92, figs 1–5.

Notophthiracarus zebra: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Notophthiracarus zebrus: Niedbala 2017: 141, fig. 95.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka, (Balogh 1962a); Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Ranomafana National Park, Reservation Expérimentale de Vohimana (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus Perty, 1841

Phthiracarus anonymus Grandjean, 1933

Phthiracarus anonymus Grandjean, 1933: 313, figs 3a–b.

Phthiracarus anonymus: Niedbala, 2001: 12, figs 1–3.

Phthiracarus anonymus: Mahunka 2002b: 7.
Phthiracarus anonymus: Niedbala 2004a: 332.
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) anonymus: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus anonymus: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.
Phthiracarus anonymus: Niedbala 2017: 64, fig. 39.
Phthiracarus anonymous (sic!): Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, (Niedbala 2001); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Border of Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus baloghorum (Mahunka, 1997)

Phthiracarus insularis: Balogh, 1962a: 149, figs 46–49.
Archiphthiracarella bulbifera Mahunka, 1996a: 18, figs 1–5.
Archiphthiracarella insularis: Mahunka 1996a: 20, figs 6–11.
Phthiracarus insularis: Mahunka 1997a: 117.
Archiphthiracarella baloghorum Mahunka, 1997b: 86.
Phthiracarus minor: Niedbala 2001: 15, figs 33–39.
Archiphthiracarella baloghorum: Mahunka 2002b: 7.
Archiphthiracarella bulbifera: Mahunka 2002b: 7.
Phthiracarus minor: Niedbala 2004a: 332.
Phthiracarus baloghorum: Niedbala 2008: 6.
Phthiracarus baloghorum: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.
Phthiracarus baloghorum: Niedbala 2017: 64, fig. 40.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. La Mandraka (Balogh 1962a *P. insularis*); Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996a *A. bulbifera*, *A. insularis*); Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a *A. baloghorum*); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a *P. baloghorum*); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a *P. baloghorum*, Niedbala 2017 *P. baloghorum*); Ambohitantely Special Reserve, Andasibe National Park, Andasibe-Mantadia Nati

onal Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Beforona commune, Border of Andasibe National Park, Ranomafana National Park, (Niedbala 2017 *P. baloghorum*).

Phthiracarus crispus Hammer, 1972

Phthiracarus crispus Hammer, 1972: 9, fig. 5.
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) crispus: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus crispus: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.
Phthiracarus crispus: Niedbala 2017: 67, fig. 41.
Phthiracarus crispus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Pantropical, eastern part.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus lentulus (C. L. Koch, 1841)

Hoplophora lentula C. L. Koch, 1841: 32, 16.
Phthiracarus (Phthiracarus) lentulus: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus lentulus: Niedbala 2017: 67, fig. 42.

Distribution. Holarctic, and Afrotropical (Angola, Madagascar).

Localities in Madagascar. Border of Andasibe National Park, Ranomafana National Park, Réservation Expérimentale de Vohimana, (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus ochthus Niedbala, 2001

Phthiracarus ochthus Niedbala, 2001: 16, figs 46–47.
Phthiracarus ochthus: Mahunka 2002b: 8.
Phthiracarus ochthus: Niedbala 2004a: 332.
Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) ochthus: Subías 2004: 55.
Phthiracarus ochthus: Niedbala 2017: 71, fig. 44.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Localities in Madagascar. Fianarantsoa, Befingotra (Niedbala 2001); Andasibe National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus paracrispus

Niedbala & Starý, 2016

Phthiracarus paracrispus Niedbala & Starý, 2016b: 489, fig. 3.

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) paracrispus: Subías 2017: 90.

Phthiracarus paracrispus: Niedbala 2017: fig. 45.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Ankarafantsika National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016b, Niedbala 2017); Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus parapocsi Niedbala, 2001

Phthiracarus parapocsi Niedbala, 2001: 17, figs 52–56.

Phthiracarus parapocsi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Phthiracarus parapocsi: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Fianarantsoa (Niedbala 2001).

Phthiracarus pygmaeus Balogh, 1958

Phthiracarus pygmaeus Balogh, 1958: 32.

Phthiracarus pygmaeus: Niedbala 2017: 75, fig. 47.

Distribution. Pantropical.

Locality in Madagascar: Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala 2017).

Phthiracarus ranomafanensis Niedbala & Starý, 2016

Phthiracarus ranomafanensis Niedbala & Starý, 2016b: 491, fig. 4.

Phthiracarus ranomafanensis: Niedbala 2017: 75, fig. 48.

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) ranomafanensis: Subías 2017: 90.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Ranomafana National Park (Niedbala & Starý 2016b).

Plonaphacarus Niedbala, 1986

Plonaphacarus kugohi (Aoki, 1959)

Hoplophthiracarus kugohi Aoki, 1959: 17, fig. 12.

Plonaphacarus kugohi: Niedbala 2001: 21, figs 97–101.

Plonaphacarus kugohi: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Plonaphacarus kugohi: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Plonaphacarus kugohi: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Plonaphacarus kugohi: Niedbala 2017: 78, fig. 49.

Distribution. Pantropical, Subtropical and southern Palaearctic regions.

Localities in Madagascar: Foulpointe (Niedbala 2001); Montagne de Francais (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala 2017).

Plonaphacarus machadoi (Balogh, 1958)

Steganacarus machadoi Balogh, 1958: 33.

Plonaphacarus machadoi: Niedbala 2017: 78, fig. 50.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Localities in Madagascar: Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala 2017).

Plonaphacarus persimilis Niedbala, 1994

Plonaphacarus persimilis Niedbala, 1994: 48, figs 23–25, 32–35.

Plonaphacarus persimilis: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 589.

Plonaphacarus persimilis: Niedbala 2017: 78, fig. 51.

Distribution. Afrotropical species, eastern part.

Locality in Madagascar: Montagne de Francais (Niedbala & Starý 2016a, Niedbala 2017).

Plonaphacarus tanzicus (Mahunka, 1993)

Hoplophthiracarus (Plonaphacarus) tanzicus Mahunka, 1993b: 91, figs 1–7.

Plonaphacarus tanzicus: Niedbala 2017: 82, fig. 52.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan.

Locality in Madagascar: Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala 2017).

Protophthiracarus Balogh, 1972

Protophthiracarus araios Niedbala, 2001

Protophthiracarus araios Niedbala, 2001: 44, figs 338–342.

Protophthiracarus araios: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Protophthiracarus araios: Niedbala 2004a: 332.

Protophthiracarus araios: Niedbala & Starý 2016a: 590.

Protophthiracarus araios: Niedbala 2017: 96, fig. 61.

Protophthiracarus araios: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Foulpointe (Niedbala 2001); Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala & Starý 2016a); Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala 2017).

Protophthiracarus mahunkai Niedbala & Starý, 2013

Protophthiracarus mahunkai Niedbala & Starý, 2013: 340, figs 2A–G.

Protophthiracarus mahunkai: Niedbala 2017: 96, fig. 62.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Special Reserve (Niedbala & Starý 2013, Niedbala 2017); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park, Ankarafantsika National Park, Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Montagne de Francais (Niedbala 2017).

CROTONIOIDEA Thorell, 1876

MALACONOTHRIDAE Berlese, 1916

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus)* Berlese, 1904**

***Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus)* cf. *monodactylus* (Michael, 1888)**

Nothrus monodactylus Michael, 1888: 528. pl. XLV, figs 10–14.

Malaconothrus (Malaconothrus) monodactylus: Subías 2004: 61.

Distribution. Holarctic and Neotropical.

New record. Ranomafana, E from Fianarantsoa, soil samples from litter of tropical rain forest, 24–26.09.1979, leg. D. Balázs. (Afr-311).

Remarks. This species is new to the fauna of Madagascar.

***Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus)* Subías, 2004**

***Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus) subrasus* (Balogh, 1962)**

Malaconothrus subrasus Balogh, 1962a: 125, figs 7–8.

Malaconothrus subrasus: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Malaconothrus subrasus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 76, pl. 131: figs 7–8.

Tyrphonostrus (Cristonostrus) subrasus: Subías 2014: 103.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a).

NOTHRIDAE Berlese, 1896

***Nothrus* C. L. Koch, 1836**

***Nothrus madagascarensis* Mahunka, 2000**

Nothrus madagascarensis Mahunka, 2000b: 21, figs 1–4.

Nothrus madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 9.

Distribution. Pantropical: Neotropical, Oriental (Borneo), Ethiopian (Guinea Ecuatorial: I. Bioko [Fernando Poo] and Kenya) and Hawaii.

Locality in Madagascar. between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 2000b).

NANHERMANNIIDAE Sellnick, 1928

***Masthermannia* Berlese, 1913**

***Masthermannia hauseri* Mahunka, 2009**

Masthermannia hauseri Mahunka, 2009c: 342, figs 5–7.

Masthermannia hauseri: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) Berlese, 1913

***Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) milloti*
Balogh, 1960**

Nanhermannia milloti Balogh, 1960: 7, figs 1–2.
Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 1997a: 118.
Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Nanhermannia milloti: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 61.
Nanhermannia (Nanhermannia) milloti: Subías 2004: 68.
Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2009a: 96, figs 10–11.
Nanhermannia milloti: Mahunka 2009c: 339.
Nanhermannia milloti: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjahandriana (Balogh 1960); Manjakatempo Forest Station (Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

New records. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W slope at 1–300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859); Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917); Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and *Pandanus* ssp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921).

HERMANNIIDAE Sellnick, 1928

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) Berlese, 1916

***Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) exornata*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Phyllhermannia exornata Balogh, 1962a: 127, figs 9–11.

Phyllhermannia exornata: Woas 1981: 44.

Phyllhermannia exornata: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Phyllhermannia exornata (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 59, pl. 111, figs 11–12.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) exornata: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

***Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) pauliani*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Phyllhermannia pauliani Balogh, 1962a: 128, figs 12–13.

Phyllhermannia pauliani: Woas 1981: 44.

Phyllhermannia pauliani: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Phyllhermannia pauliani: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 59, pl. 110, figs 11–12.

Hermannia (Phyllhermannia) pauliani: Subías 2004: 70.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ambatovositra (Balogh 1962a).

TRHYPOCHTHONIIDAE Willmann, 1931

***Trhypochthoniellus* Willmann, 1928**

***Trhypochthoniellus longisetus setosus*
Willmann, 1928**

Trhypochthonius longisetus Berlese, 1904: 27, fig. 2:44.

Trhypochthoniellus longisetus: Mahunka 2011a: 3, figs 1–4.

Trhypochthoniellus longisetus f. *setosus*: Schabetsberger et al. 2013: 331.

Trhypochthoniellus longisetus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Trhypochthoniellus longisetus setosus: Subías 2010: 92.

Distribution. Continental Southeast Asia, Palearctic and Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2011a).

Remarks. Looking at the synonym list and the publication list it seems that the species was found

twice in Madagascar, in the same national park. At first Mahunka cited it without subspecies designation (Mahunka 2011a). When it was found again in the same national park – but with different collecting method –, he cited it with subspecies designation (Schabetsberger *et al.* 2013). As the nominotypical subspecies is cosmopolitan and the subspecies *T. l. setosus* is known to have more restricted distribution (Corpuz-Raros & Ermilov 2020), we keep this subspecies in the list.

HERMANIELLOIDEA Grandjean, 1934

HERMANNIELLIDAE Grandjean, 1934

***Hermanniella* Berlese, 1908**

***Hermanniella madagascarensis* Balogh, 1962**

Hermanniella madagascarensis Balogh, 1962b: 419, figs 1–4.

Hermanniella madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Hermanniella madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 96, pl. 154, figs 9–11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

Hermanniella vohimana

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Hermanniella vohimana Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 128, figs 2a–d.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

PLASMOBATIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1961

Malgachebates

Fernandez, Cleva & Theron, 2011

***Malgachebates peyrierasi* Fernandez, Cleva & Theron, 2011**

Malgachebates peyrierasi Fernandez, Cleva & Theron, 2011: 62, figs 1–53.

Distribution. Ethiopian and Neotropical.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankarongambe forest (10 km E/SE of Ambohidray) (Fernandez, Cleva & Theron 2011).

PLATEREMAEOIDEA Trägårdh, 1926

PLATEREMAEIDAE Trägårdh, 1926

***Paralopheremaeus* Paschoal, 1987**

***Paralopheremaeus legendrei* (Balogh, 1962)**

Plateremaeus legendrei Balogh, 1962b: 421, figs 5–6.

Paralopheremaeus legendrei: Paschoal 1987: 351.

Paralopheremaeus legendrei: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Plateremaeus legendrei: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 106, pl. 167, fig. 12., pl. 168, fig. 1.

Distribution. Ethiopian region (Madagascar and Kenya) and Sri Lanka.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

PHEROLIODIDAE PASCHOAL, 1987

***Malgacheliodes* Fernandez & Cleva, 2010**

Malgacheliodes guillaumeti

Fernandez & Cleva, 2010

Malgacheliodes guillaumeti Fernandez & Cleva, 2010b: 419, figs 1–4.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Amindramiova (Fernandez & Cleva 2010b).

***Nooliodes* Paschoal, 1989**

***Nooliodes glaber* (Balogh, 1962)**

Plateremaeus glaber Balogh, 1962b: 421, figs 7–8.

Nooliodes glaber: Paschoal 1989: 180.

Nooliodes glaber: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Nooliodes glaber: Mahunka 2002b: 10.

Nooliodes glaber: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 106, pl. 169, figs 1–2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b); Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve, (Mahunka 1997a).

CEPHEOIDEA Berlese, 1896

MICROTEGEIDAE Balogh, 1972

***Microtegeus* Balogh, 1972**

***Microtegeus paracervus* Mahunka, 1997**

Microtegeus cervus Mahunka, 1996b: 109, figs 1–5.
Microtegeus paracervus: Mahunka 1997b: 86.
Microtegeus cervus: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Microtegeus paracervus: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mount Ambatokirijy at the S edge of Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

***Microtegeus zigzag* Mahunka, 2011**

Microtegeus zigzag Mahunka, 2011b: 46, figs: 3a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) (Mahunka 2011b).

NOSYBEIDAE Mahunka, 1993

***Nosybea* Mahunka, 1993**

***Nosybea genavensis* Mahunka, 1993**

Nosybea genavensis Mahunka, 1993a: 298, figs 17–25.
Nosybea genavensis: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Nosybea genavensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 255, pl. 353, figs 2–3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a).

POLYPTEROZETOIDEA Grandjean, 1959

NODOCEPHEIDAE Piffli, 1972

***Nodocepheus* Hammer, 1958**

***Nodocepheus baloghi* Mahunka, 1983**

Nodocepheus baloghi Mahunka, 1983b: 164, figs 41–43, 46.

Nodocepheus baloghi: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011: 126.

Distribution. Tanzania and Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

MICROZETOIDEA Grandjean, 1936

MICROZETIDAE Grandjean, 1936

***Acaroceras (Malgoceras)* Mahunka, 1993**

***Acaroceras (Malgoceras) helleri* Mahunka, 1993**

Acaroceras (Malgoceras) helleri Mahunka, 1993a: 301, figs 26–29.

Acaroceras (Malgoceras) helleri: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Acaroceras (Malgoceras) helleri: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Malgoceras helleri: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 282, pl. 389, fig. 7.

Acaroceras (Malgoceras) helleri: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a, Mahunka 1997a, Mahunka 2009c).

***Berlesezetes* Mahunka, 1980**

***Berlesezetes africanus* (Balogh, 1958)**

Microzetes africanus Balogh, 1958: 28.

Microzetes africanus: Mahunka 1999a: 67.

Microzetes africanus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Berlesezetes africanus: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Berlesezetes ornatissimus ornatissimus: Subías 2004: 87.

Berlesezetes ornatissimus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Democratic Republic of Congo (Balogh 1958) and Madagascar (Mahunka 1999, 2009c).

Localities in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 1999a); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

Remarks. One can see that the material collected in the Ambohitra National Park ("Mad-89/8") was first identified as *B. cf. auxiliaris* (Mahunka 1997a), then the same locality is used for *B. africanus* (Mahunka 2009c). We checked the material in the HNHM collection and found that from the originally identified 5 *B. cf. auxiliaris* specimens 1 individual was later identified as *B. africanus*.

The species was described by Balogh (1958) from Belgian Congo [currently Democratic Republic of the Congo]. In the description, Balogh admits that except for one character the species is similar to *M. auxiliaris* Grandjean, 1936. In 1999 – dealing with Madagascan material – Mahunka writes: „*The status of the species has been ambiguous ever since its description, for many authors, including myself, considered it to be synonymous with Microzetes auxiliaris. This is the first time when I found a specimen on which the guttiform incision, as described by Balogh is clearly seen just beside the outer apex of the lamellae*” (Mahunka 1999a). He was also able to investigate the types of the species preserved in the Hungarian Natural History Museum (Mahunka 2005). The last draft of the present monograph – prepared by Mahunka and Mahunka-Papp in 2011 – holds on this opinion, *i.e.* *B. africanus* is treated as a separate species. These are the reasons why we cite it here as a separate species, not as a synonym of *B. ornatissimus* (Berlese, 1913), as Subías (2004) and Ermilov & Frolov (2022a) treat it. Further investigations and/or molecular evidences are needed to decide about the synonymies.

***Berlesezetes cf. auxiliaris* (Grandjean, 1936)**

Microzetes auxiliaris Grandjean, 1936: 138, figs 1–4.

Berlesezetes cf. auxiliaris: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Berlesezetes cf. auxiliaris: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Berlesezetes ornatissimus ornatissimus: Subías 2004: 87.

Distribution. Questionably circumtropical (Mahunka 2005).

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

Remarks. Since many years there has been a debate on the identity of *B. ornatissimus* (Berlese, 1913) and *B. auxiliaris* (Grandjean, 1936) (see J. & P. Balogh 2002; Subías 2004; Mahunka 2005). From the literature we know that Sándor Mahunka has seen the types of *B. ornatissimus* (Mahunka 1980), and he was the first who has found and made drawings of *B. ornatissimus* since its description (Mahunka 1988). At that time he pointed out that: “*The difference from B. auxiliaris Grandjean, 1936 is very small, thus a revision is necessary.*” (Mahunka 1988). Later, he also has studied *B. auxiliaris* well, as he found topotypical individuals which he regarded “*nearly identical with the ones that Grandjean described and drew*” (Mahunka 2005). We do not want to make taxonomic decisions on this issue, nor do we want to cause a loss of information. Thus, compiling the facts listed here with the remarks discussed above by *B. africanus*, we cite *B. cf. auxiliaris* as a separate species (and not as a synonym of *B. ornatissimus* (Berlese, 1913), as Subías (2004) and Ermilov & Frolov (2022a) treat it). Mahunka cited it always with uncertainty (“*cf.*”), *i.e.* not as *B. auxiliaris* (even in the last drafts of the present monograph – prepared by Mahunka and Mahunka-Papp in 2011). Once he also proposed a new African species of the genus (Mahunka 2005) but without referring to that as *B. cf. auxiliaris*. We may never find out what he meant at that time (Mahunka 2005) but further investigations can decide on the identity of this *B. cf. auxiliaris* material. Further investigations and/or molecular evidences are also needed to decide about the possible synonymies in the genus.

Comorozetes Mahunka, 1994

***Comorozetes concurvatus* Mahunka, 1999**

Comorozetes concurvatus Mahunka, 1999a: 61, figs 1–4.

Comorozetes concurvatus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha south of the Andasibe National Park, Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 1999a).

New records. Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and Pandanus ssp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921); Prov. Antsiranana [anciennement Diego-Suarez], Sous-préf. Antsiranana: Parc National "Montagne d'Ambre" (= Ambohitra). près de la "Petite Cascade", forêt primaire. prélèvement de sol dans les angles formés par les contreforts d'un grand arbre, 980 m, 23.11.1989, leg. B. Hauser (Mad-98/7).

Remarks. During collection research we have recognized that the label at the holotype refers to a different locality than published: Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and Pandanus ssp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921). However, we found no vials of the species with the published locality (i.e. No. 9890). Additionally, there is a non-type vial in the collection with this locality data (i.e. No. 9878). In the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka the published locality is connected to the holotype. Thus, in this case we suppose that an erroneous labelling happened. Altogether we found four vials in the collection: one with the holotype, one with the paratype, and two vials which are published here as *New records* (see above).

Comorozetes corrugatus Mahunka, 1997

Comorozetes corrugatus Mahunka, 1997a: 123, figs 5–10.

Comorozetes corrugatus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Comorozetes corrugatus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 287, pl. 393. fig. 8.

Comorozetes corrugatus: Mahunka 2009a: 92.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve, Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a), Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

New records. Prov. Antsiranana [formerly Diego Snarez] Sub-Pref Antsiranana: National Park "Montagne Amber", drive to the "Petit Lac" primary forest soil sampling in the angles by the foothills of a large dead tree. 1090 m, 24.11.1989, leg. B. Hauser (Mad-89/19), Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

Hymenozetes Balogh, 1962

Hymenozetes csuzdii Mahunka, 2009

Hymenozetes csuzdii Mahunka, 2009a: 116, figs 50–52.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

Hymenozetes mirabilis Balogh, 1962

Hymenozetes mirabilis Balogh, 1962a: 142, figs 32–33.

Hymenozetes mirabilis: Mahunka 1990b: 204, figs 24–28.

Hymenozetes mirabilis: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Hymenozetes mirabilis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 288, pl. 394. fig. 9.

Hymenozetes mirabilis: Mahunka 2009a: 118.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. La Mandraka (Balogh 1962a).

Hymenozetes quadricornutus Mahunka, 1993

Hymenozetes quadricornutus Mahunka, 1993a: 303, figs 30–33.

Hymenozetes quadricornutus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.
Hymenozetes quadricornutus (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 289, pl. 394. fig. 10.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a).

***Hymenozetes reticulatus* Mahunka, 1996**

Hymenozetes reticulatus Mahunka, 1996b: 110, figs 6–10.

Hymenozetes reticulatus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b).

***Hymenozetes stellifer* Mahunka, 1999**

Hymenozetes stellifer Mahunka, 1999a: 64, figs 5–7.

Hymenozetes stellifer: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park, between Ambatolaona and Mandraka (Mahunka 1999a).

***Hymenozetes verticillatus* Mahunka, 1997**

Hymenozetes verticillatus Mahunka, 1997a: 126, figs 11–13.

Hymenozetes verticillatus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Hymenozetes verticillatus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 289, pl. 394. fig. 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a).

Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) Balogh, 1962

***Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) cornutus*
(Mahunka, 1999)**

Magoebazetes cornutus Mahunka, 1999a: 65, figs 8–11.

Magoebazetes cornutus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) cornutus: Subías 2022: 315.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 1999a).

***Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) lokobensis*
Mahunka, 1993**

Rhopalozetes lokobensis Mahunka, 1993a: 308, figs 42–45.

Rhopalozetes lokobensis: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Rhopalozetes lokobensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 290, pl. 395, fig. 8.

Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) lokobensis: Subías 2022: 315.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a).

***Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) madecassus*
Mahunka, 1993**

Rhopalozetes madecassus Mahunka, 1993a: 308, figs 38–41.

Rhopalozetes madecassus: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Rhopalozetes medecassus (sic!): Mahunka 1999a: 68.

Rhopalozetes madecassus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Rhopalozetes madecassus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 290, pl. 394. fig. 7.

Rhopalozetes madecassus: Mahunka 2009a: 92.

Rhopalozetes madecassus: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) madecassus: Subías 2022: 315.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a, Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 1999a, Mahunka 2010a).

***Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) milloti*
Balogh, 1962**

Rhopalozetes milloti Balogh, 1962a: 143, figs 34–35.

Rhopalozetes milloti: Mahunka 1990b: 206, figs 29–31.

Rhopalozetes milloti: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Rhopalozetes milloti: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 290, pl. 395. fig. 9.

Rhopalozetes (Rhopalozetes) milloti: Subías 2022: 315.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. La Mandraka (Balogh 1962a).

***Schalleriella* Engelbrecht, 1972**

***Schalleriella nosybe* (Mahunka, 1993)**

Megazetes nosybe Mahunka, 1993a: 306, figs 34–37.

Megazetes nosybe: Mahunka 1997a: 118.

Megazetes nosybe: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Mahunkaceras nosibe (sic!): Balogh & Balogh, 2002: 285, fig. 392: 4.

Schalleriella nosybe: Subías 2011: 158.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993a, Mahunka 1997a).

***Schalleriella phaseola* Mahunka, 2011**

Schalleriella phaseola Mahunka, 2011b: 48, figs: 4a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011b).

***Vermacarus* Balogh & Mahunka, 1980**

***Vermacarus armatus* Mahunka, 1997**

Vermacarus armatus Mahunka, 1997a: 126, figs 14–16.

Vermacarus armatus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Vermacarus armatus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 284, pl. 391, fig. 2.

Vermacarus armatus: Mahunka 2009a: 92.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjakatempo Forest Station (Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

AMEROIDEA Bulanova-Zachvatkina, 1957

AMERIDAE Grandjean, 1965

***Hymenobelba* Balogh, 1962**

***Hymenobelba exclamationis* Mahunka, 2010**

Hymenobelba exclamationis Mahunka, 2010b: 63, figs 1–6.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010b).

***Hymenobelba flagellatissima* Mahunka, 2009**

Hymenobelba flagellatissima Mahunka, 2009b: 48, figs 1–3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

New record. Prov. Antsiranana [formerly Diego Suarez] Sub-Pref Antsiranana: National Park "Montagne Amber" (= Ambohitra), drive to the "Petit Lac" primary forest soil sampling in the angles by the foothills of a large dead tree. 1090 m, 24.XI.1989; leg. B. Hauser (Mad-89/19), Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antani-naomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E. 29. July 1998. Coll. T. Pócs. (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

***Hymenobelba ypsilon* Balogh, 1962**

Hymenobelba ypsilon Balogh, 1962a: 423, figs 9–11.

Hymenobelba ypsilon: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Hymenobelba ypsilon: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 104, pl. 165, figs 10–11.

Distribution. Madagascar and North East India.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962a).

***Pteramerus* Balogh, 1962**

***Pteramerus clypeatus* Mahunka, 2010**

Pteramerus clypeatus Mahunka, 2010b: 65, figs 7–17.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010b).

New records. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917); Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and *Pandanus* ssp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921).

***Pteramerus draco* Balogh, 1962**

Pteramerus draco Balogh, 1962a: 136, figs 26–28.

Pteramerus draco: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Pteramerus draco: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 104, pl. 165, figs 1–2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a).

EREMULIDAE Grandjean, 1965

***Caveremulus* Mahunka, 1983**

***Caveremulus cordisetus* Mahunka, 1983**

Caveremulus cordisetus Mahunka, 1983a: 103, figs 5–6.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Mahunka 1993: 291.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Mahunka 1994: 49.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 105, pl. 167, figs 1–2.

Caveremulus cordisetus: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana (Mahunka 1983a); Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993); Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1994, Mahunka 1997a, Mahunka 2009c).

New record. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

***Caveremulus foliaceus* Mahunka, 2009**

Caveremulus foliaceus Mahunka, 2009c: 343, figs 8–10.

Caveremulus foliaceus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c),

New record. Peyrieras, Causse de Kelifelly. Forest humus and litter from dry forest. 20–30.11.1974, leg. D. Smith (Afr-JB-1).

***Caveremulus salicinus* Mahunka, 2009**

Caveremulus salicinus Mahunka, 2009c: 345, figs 11–13.

Caveremulus salicinus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

DAMAEOLIDAE GRANDJEAN, 1965

***Fosseremus* Grandjean, 1954**

***Fosseremus laciniatus* (Berlese, 1905)**

Dameosoma laciniatum Berlese, 1905: 236.

Fosseremus quadripertitus: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Fosseremus laciniatus: Subías 2004: 103.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan (except Antarctica).

Locality in Madagascar. Mangabé Island, Antongil Bay (Mahunka 2011b).

***Gressittolus* Balogh, 1970**

***Gressittolus ocellatus* (Mahunka, 2000)**

Damaeolus ocellatus Mahunka, 2000b: 23, figs 5–6.

Damaeolus ocellatus: Mahunka 2002b: 10.
Gressittolus ocellatus: Baran, Ayyildiz & Subías 2010: 344.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. N of Andovoranto, between Artdombo and Andovoa (Mahunka 2000b).

EREMOBELBIDAE Balogh, 1961

***Eremobelba* Berlese, 1908**

Eremobelba cellulosa Mahunka, 1997

Eremobelba cellulosa Mahunka, 1997a: 130, figs 17–21.
Eremobelba cellulosa: Mahunka 2002b: 11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

RHYNCHORIBATIDAE BALOGH, 1961

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*)**

Miko, 2016

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *genavensium* (Mahunka, 1997)**

Rhynchoribates genavensium Mahunka, 1997a: 150, figs 54–60.
Rhynchoribates genavensium: Balogh & Balogh 1999a: 14, figs 7–8.
Rhynchoribates genavensium: Mahunka 2002b: 13.
Rhynchoribates genavensium: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 134, pl. 196, figs 8–9.
Eurhynchoribates genavensium: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park; Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *robinsoni* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhynchoribates robinsoni Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 23–24.

Rhynchoribates robinsoni: Balogh & Balogh 1999a: 14, fig. 15.

Rhynchoribates robinsoni: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Rhynchoribates robinsoni: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 134, pl. 197, fig. 4.

Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *robinsoni*: Miko 2016: 133.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

New records. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W-slope at 100–300 m alt. 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859); Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917); Toamasina Province, Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park and the Antananarivo Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Afr-923).

***Eurhynchoribates* (*Eurhynchoribates*) *subaequalis* (Balogh, 1962)**

Rhynchoribates subaequalis Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 21–22.
Rhynchoribates subaequalis: Balogh & Balogh 1999a: 14, fig. 4.
Rhynchoribates subaequalis: Mahunka 2002b: 13.
Rhynchoribates subaequalis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 134, pl. 196, fig. 5.
Eurhynchoribates (*Eurhynchoribates*) *subaequalis*: Miko 2016: 133.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

ZETORCHESTOIDEA Michael, 1898

ZETORCHESTIDAE Michael, 1898

Zetorchestes Berlese, 1888

***Zetorchestes phylliferus* Mahunka, 1983**

- Zetorchestes (Phyllorcheses) phylliferus* Mahunka, 1983a: 105, figs 7–8.
Zetorchestes (Phyllorcheses) phylliferus: Mahunka 2002b: 11.
Zetorchestes phylliferus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 227, pl. 314, figs 4–5.
Zetorchestes (Phyllorcheses) phylligerus (sic!): Mahunka 2009c: 339.
Zetorchestes phylliferus: Kolesnikov & Leonov 2021: 558.
Zetorchestes phylliferus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Afrotropical and Oriental.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana (Mahunka 1983a); Montagne d’Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c); Montagne d’Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

New records. Vohimana Reserve, primary forest. 17.04.2008, leg. Cs. Csuzdi (Afr-996); Ambohitantely Forest Reserve E of Manonkazo village (Ankasabz town). Relic xerophyllous (dry evergreen) plateau forest at 1500–1530 m alt. 18°09′ 23″S, 47°17′02″E. 05–06.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9444) (Afr 857).

GUSTAVIOIDEA Oudemans, 1900

ASTEGISTIDAE Balogh, 1961

***Cultroribula* Berlese, 1908**

***Cultroribula bicuspidata* Mahunka, 1978**

- Cultroribula bicuspidata* Mahunka, 1978b: 317, figs 17–20.
Cultroribula bicuspidata: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Distribution. Pantropical (except Australian).

Locality in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

CERATOPPIIDAE Kunst, 1971

***Trichoppia* Balogh, 1961**

***Trichoppia longiseta* Balogh, 1960**

- Trichoppia longiseta* Balogh, 1960: 20, figs 20–22.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 1990b: 206, figs 32–35.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 1993: 291.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 1997a: 119.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 2002b: 11.
Trichoppia longiseta: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 244, pl. 338, figs 1–2.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 2009a: 91.
Trichoppia longiseta: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjakandriana, La Mandraka (Balogh 1960); Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1993); Manjakatempo Forest Station (Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

GUSTAVIIDAE Oudemans, 1900

***Gustavia* Kramer, 1879**

***Gustavia ornata* Mahunka 2011**

- Gustavia ornata* Mahunka, 2011b: 49, figs 5a–g.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2011b).

***Gustavia sineornata* Mahunka, 2011**

- Gustavia sineornata* Mahunka, 2011b: 52, figs 6a–d.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Peyrieras, Causse de Kelifelly (Mahunka 2011b).

CARABODOIDEA C. L. Koch, 1837

CARABODIDAE C. L. Koch, 1837

Afticarabodes

Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

- Afticarabodes anjavidilavai* Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013**

- Afticarabodes anjavidilavai* Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013b: 465, figs. 1–25.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Anjavidilava (Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013b).

***Antongilibodes* Fernandez, Theron, Leiva,
Rollard & Tiedt, 2014**

***Antongilibodes paulae* Fernandez, Theron, Leiva,
Rollard & Tiedt, 2014**

Antongilibodes paulae Fernandez, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt, 2014: 309, figs 39–72.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Mangabe (Fernandez, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt 2014).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes)*
Hammer, 1966**

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) albidus*
(Balogh, 1960)**

Carabodes albidus Balogh, 1960: 22, figs 23–24.
Carabodes albidus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.
Austrocarabodes albidus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 240, pl. 333, figs 1–2.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) albidus: Subías 2004: 148.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Manjakandriana La Mandraka (Balogh 1960).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) blancharti*
Mahunka, 2009**

Austrocarabodes blancharti Mahunka, 2009a: 100, figs 22–26.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) blancharti: Subías 2010: 282.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

New record. Mangabé Island, Antongil Bay. Primary rain forest, rotten wood. 19.02.1977. leg. W. L. & D. L. Brown (Afr-JB2).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) cellularis*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Carabodes cellularis Balogh, 1962b: 425, figs 17–18.
Carabodes cellularis: Mahunka 2002b: 12.
Austrocarabodes cellularis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 240, pl. 332, figs 11–12.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) cellularis: Subías 2004: 148.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes)*
lateoalveolatus Mahunka, 2009**

Austrocarabodes lateoalveolatus Mahunka, 2009a: 102, figs 27–29.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) lateoalveolatus: Subías 2010: 283.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) lunaris*
(Balogh, 1962)**

Carabodes lunaris Balogh, 1962b: 423, figs 15–16.
Carabodes lunaris: Mahunka 1993: 291.
Carabodes lunaris: Mahunka 2002b: 12.
Austrocarabodes lunaris: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 238, pl. 329, figs 10–11.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) lunaris: Subías 2004: 148.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.
Localities in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b); Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1993).

***Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes)*
madagascarensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020**

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) madagascarensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020c: 354, figs 1–4.
Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) madagascarensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020c).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) mixtus
Mahunka, 1996

Austrocarabodes mixtus Mahunka, 1996b: 113, figs 11–17.

Austrocarabodes mixtus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) mixtus: Subías 2004: 148.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) parapustulatus
Mahunka, 2009

Austrocarabodes parapustulatus Mahunka, 2009a: 105, figs 30–32.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) parapustulatus: Subías 2010: 283.

Austrocarabodes parapustulatus: Ermilov & Starý 2020c: 360, figs 5–7.

Austrocarabodes parapustulatus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020c).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) planisetus
Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Austrocarabodes planisetus Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 130, figs 4a–e.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) planisetus: Subías 2014: 285.

Austrocarabodes planisetus: Ermilov & Starý 2020c: 364, figs 8–10.

Austrocarabodes planisetus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011); Montagne d'Ambre National Park, (Ermilov & Starý 2020c).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) pustuloreticulatus
Mahunka, 2009

Austrocarabodes pustuloreticulatus Mahunka, 2009a: 107, figs 33–39.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) pustuloreticulatus: Subías 2010: 283.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) semilunatus
Mahunka, 2011

Austrocarabodes semilunatus Mahunka, 2011b: 54, figs 7a–d.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) semilunatus: Subías 2012: 279.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Peyrieras, Causse de Kelifelly (Mahunka 2011b).

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) spathulatus
Mahunka, 1978

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) spathulatus Mahunka, 1978a: 204, figs 68–70.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) spathulatus: Ermilov & Starý 2020c: 369.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) spathulatus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Madagascar and Reunion.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020c).

Austrocarabodes (Austroflexa) Subías, 2019

Austrocarabodes (Austroflexa) armatus
Mahunka, 2009

Austrocarabodes armatus Mahunka, 2009a: 98, figs 15–21.

Austrocarabodes (Austrocarabodes) armatus: Subías 2010: 282.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

New record. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

Bovicarabodes

Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

Bovicarabodes deharvengi Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

Bovicarabodes deharvengi Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013a: 4, figs: 1–32.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Marositry (Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013a).

Bovicarabodes fortdauphini Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

Bovicarabodes fortdauphini Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013a: 13, figs: 50–69.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. St. Luke Coastal Forest (Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013a).

Bovicarabodes jacquelinae Fernandez, Theron, Rollard, Leiva & Tiedt, 2016

Bovicarabodes jacquelinae Fernandez, Theron, Rollard, Leiva & Tiedt, 2016: 80, figs: 1–5.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Mangabe (Fernandez, Theron, Rollard, Leiva & Tiedt 2016).

Bovicarabodes levyi

Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

Bovicarabodes levyi Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013a: 8, figs: 33–49.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Anjavililava (Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013a).

Carabodes (Klapperiches) C. L. Koch, 1835

Carabodes (Klapperiches) afrominusculus

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011

Carabodes afrominusculus Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 132, figs 5a–c.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) afrominusculus: Subías 2014: 289.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Forest Reserve (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

Carabodes (Klapperiches) andasibe

Mahunka, 1993

Carabodes andasibe Mahunka, 1993a: 311, figs 46–49.

Carabodes andasibe: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Carabodes abdasibe (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 232, pl. 319, figs 11–12.

Carabodes (Klapperiches) andasibe: Subías 2004: 150.
Carabodes andasibe: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve before Andasibe (Mahunka 1993a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

Cavaecarabodes Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo, 2014

Cavaecarabodes anouchkae

Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo, 2014

Cavaecarabodes anouchkae Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo, 2014b: 547, figs 36–53.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Manankaza Forest Station Ambohitantely (Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014b).

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) Balogh, 1958

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) germani

Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo, 2014

Congocepheus germani Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo, 2014b: 536, figs 1–12.

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) germani: Subías 2018: 302.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ivontaka (15 km au S. de Mananara) (Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014b).

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) involutus

Mahunka, 1997

Congocepheus involutus Mahunka, 1997a: 133, figs 22–24.

Congocepheus involutus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Congocepheus involutus: Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Tiedt 2013: 553, figs 1–5.

Congocepheus (Congocepheus) involutus: Subías 2018: 302.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a); Vanjamanitra forest (8 km SE of Anjorzorobe), Ile de Nosy Mangabe (Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Tiedt 2013).

New record. Central Plateau: Ambohitantely Forest Reserve E of Manonkazo village (Ankaszabz town). Relic xerophyllous (dry evergreen) plateau forest at 1500–1530 m alt. 18° 09'23"S, 47°17'02"E. 05–06.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9444) (Afr 857).

Machadocepheus Balogh, 1958

Machadocepheus pauliani Balogh, 1962

Machadocepheus pauliani Balogh, 1962b: 423, figs 12–14.

Machadocepheus pauliani: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Machadocepheus pauliani: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 234, pl. 323, figs 7–8.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b).

Malgasodes Mahunka, 2000

Malgasodes curvisetus Mahunka, 2000

Malgasodes curvisetus Mahunka, 2000a: 87, figs 1–4.

Malgasodes curvisetus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Malgasodes curvisetus: Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014a: 28, figs: 1–23.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2000a); Sainte Luce (Fernández, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014a).

Malgasodes hungarorum Mahunka, 2000

Malgasodes hungarorum Mahunka, 2000a: 90, figs 5–6.

Malgasodes hungarorum: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Malgasodes hungarorum: Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014a: 37, figs: 24–27.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2000a, Fernandez, Theron, Rollard & Castillo 2014a).

Rugocepheus Mahunka, 2009

Rugocepheus formosus Mahunka, 2009

Rugocepheus formosus Mahunka, 2009b: 50, figs 4–7.

Rugocepheus formosus: Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013b: 470.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

Rugocepheus joffrevillei

Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013

Rugocepheus joffrevillei Fernandez, Theron & Rollard, 2013b: 472, figs 26–60.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Joffreville (Fernandez, Theron & Rollard 2013b).

Tuberocepheus Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Tuberocepheus (Tuberocepheus)

Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Tuberocephus (Tuberocephus) longus
(Balogh, 1962)

Machadocephus longus Balogh, 1962a: 139, figs 29–31.

Machadocephus longus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Tuberocephus longus: Balogh & Mahunka 1969: 9.

Tuberocephus longus: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Tuberocephus longus: Mahunka 2011a: 5, figs 5–12.

Tuberocephus longus: Fernandez, Theron, Rollard, Leiva & Tiedt 2016: 83, figs 6–32.

Tuberocephus (Tuberocephus) longus: Subías 2017: 304.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjahandriana, Ambotolaona (Balogh 1962a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mount Maromizaha south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2011a).

Tuberocephus (Mangabebodes) Fernández, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt, 2014

Tuberocephus (Mangabebodes) kymatismosi
Fernández, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt, 2014

Mangabebodes kymatismosi Fernández, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt, 2014: 298, figs 1–38.

Tuberocephus (Mangabebodes) kymatismosi: Subías 2017: 305.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Mangabe (Fernández, Theron, Leiva, Rollard & Tiedt 2014).

OTOCEPHEIDAE Balogh, 1961

Afrotocephus (Didierotocephus)
Mahunka, 1994

Afrotocephus (Didierotocephus) berndi
Mahunka, 1994

Didierotocephus berndi Mahunka, 1994: 52, figs 8–12.

Didierotocephus berndi: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Didierotocephus berndi: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Didierotocephus berndti (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 154, pl. 222, figs 4–5.

Afrotocephus (Didierotocephus) berndi: Subías 2004: 141.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1994); 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1994, Mahunka 1997a); Manjakatempo Forest Station (Mahunka 1997a),

Leptotocephus (Leptotocephus) Balogh, 1961

Leptotocephus (Longocephus) longus
(Balogh, 1960)

Pseudotocephus longus Balogh, 1960: 25, figs 27–29.

Pseudotocephus longus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocephus longus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 153, pl. 220, fig. 7.

Leptotocephus (Longocephus) longus: Ermilov & Minor 2018: 2271.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ankazobe, Ambohitantely; Andranomalaza, Manakombahiny-Est (Balogh 1960).

Papillocephus Balogh & Mahunka, 1966

***Papillocephus decoratus* Mahunka, 1994**

Papillocephus decoratus Mahunka, 1994: 54, figs 13–17.

Papillocephus decoratus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Papillocephus decoratus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 151, pl. 218, figs 9–10.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994).

***Papillocephus reductus* Mahunka, 1994**

Papillocephus reductus Mahunka, 1994: 56, figs 18–20.

Papillocephus reductus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Papillocephus reductus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 151, pl. 218, figs 3–4.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve, Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994).

***Pseudotocepheus* Balogh, 1961**

***Pseudotocepheus atolanaro* Mahunka, 2009**

Pseudotocepheus atolanaro Mahunka, 2009b: 52, figs 8–11.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

New record. Toamasina Province, Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mt. Maromizaha, south of Andasibe Nat. Park and the Antananarivo – Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Afr-923).

***Pseudotocepheus lienhardi* Mahunka, 1993**

Pseudotocepheus lienhardi Mahunka, 1993a: 314, figs 50–53.

Pseudotocepheus lienhardi: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Pseudotocepheus lienhardi: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocepheus lienhardi: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 152, pl. 219. figs 8–9.

Distribution. Madagascar and Kenya.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1993a, Mahunka 1997a), 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a).

***Pseudotocepheus pauliani* Balogh, 1960**

Pseudotocepheus pauliani Balogh, 1960: 23, figs 25–26.

Pseudotocepheus pauliani: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocepheus pauliani: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 155, pl. 222. figs 8–9.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ambatovositra, Manakambahiny-Est (Balogh 1960).

***Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus* Balogh, 1962**

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus Balogh, 1962b: 427, figs 19–20.

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocepheus pygmaeus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 152, pl. 219. fig. 3.

Distribution. Madagascar and Mozambique.

Localities in Madagascar. Quest Tanikely (Balogh 1962b); Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

Pseudotocepheus subtilis

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Pseudotocepheus subtilis Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 133, figs 6a–d.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

***Pseudotocepheus tolanaro* Mahunka, 1997**

Pseudotocepheus tolanaro Mahunka, 1997a: 135, figs 25–27.

Pseudotocepheus tolanaro: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Pseudotocepheus tolanaro: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 152, pl. 218. figs 15–16.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a).

OPPIOIDEA Grandjean, 1951

OPPIIDAE Grandjean, 1951

OPPIINAE Sellnick, 1937

***Erioppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Erioppia corpuzrarosae* Ermilov & Starý, 2020**

Erioppia corpuzrarosae Ermilov & Starý, 2020i: 448, figs 1–3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

***Erioppia malalatinæ* (Mahunka, 2009)**

Multioppia malalatinæ Mahunka, 2009b: 54, figs 13–15.

Erioppia malalatinae: Subías 2010: 204.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

***Fusuloppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Fusuloppia neominata* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia simplex Balogh, 1962a: 129, figs 14–15.

Fusuloppia simplex: Subías & Balogh 1989: 377.

Fusuloppia simplex: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Fusuloppia simplex: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Fusuloppia simplex: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 203, pl. 282, figs 6–7.

Fusuloppia neominata: Subías 2004: 113.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankaratra, col de Faratsiho (Balogh 1962a).

***Fusuloppia variosetosa* Mahunka, 2010**

Fusuloppia variosetosa Mahunka, 2010a: 53, figs 18–22.

Fusuloppia variosetosa: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 446.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ranomafana; Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2010a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

***Goyoppia* Balogh, 1983**

***Goyoppia sexpilosa* (Balogh, 1961)**

Oppia sexpilosa Balogh, 1961: 17, fig. 15.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Balogh 1983: 53, table 16, fig. 24–4.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Subías & Balogh 1989: 377.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 226, pl. 312, fig. 3.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 446.

Goyoppia sexpilosa: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjahandriana, Ambotolaona (Balogh 1960); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 1997a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

***Lemuroppia* Mahunka, 1994**

***Lemuroppia helleri* Mahunka, 1994**

Lemuroppia helleri Mahunka, 1994: 62, figs 33–39.

Lemuroppia helleri: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Lemuroppia helleri: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Lemuroppia helleri: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 226, pl. 312, figs 1–2.

Lemuroppia helleri: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

New records. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnant in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29.07.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917); Toamasina Prov. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the NW slope of Behafotra Hill, at 250–300 m alt., with 3500 mm annual rainfall. 16°27.1-3'S, 49°47.6'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9877) (Afr-920).

***Oppia (Lasiobelba)* Aoki, 1959**

***Oppia (Lasiobelba) lemuria* Mahunka, 1997**

Lasiobelba lemuria Mahunka, 1997a: 139, figs 34–40.

Lasiobelba lemuria: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Lasiobelba lemuria: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Oppia (Lasiobelba) lemuria: Subías 2022: 195.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

***Paroppia* Hammer, 1968**

***Paroppia breviseta* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia breviseta Balogh, 1962c: 100, figs 14–16.

Paroppia breviseta: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

BRACHIOPIIINAE Subías, 1989

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) Balogh, 1983

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) sensilla (Mahunka, 2002)

Jermymia sensilla Mahunka, 2002a: 167, figs 1–4.

Jermymia sensilla: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Gressittoppia sensilla: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) sensilla: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 446.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. N of Andovoranto, between Artdombo and Andovoa (Mahunka 2002a); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2010a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) pocsi Mahunka, 2002

Gressittoppia pocsi Mahunka, 2002a: 169, figs 5–9.

Gressittoppia pocsi: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Brachioppiella (Gressittoppia) pocsi: Subías 2004: 122.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. N of Andovoranto, between Artdombo and Andovoa (Mahunka 2002a).

Leptoppia Mahunka, 1997

Leptoppia benyovszkyi Mahunka, 1996

Leptoppia benyovszkyi Mahunka, 1996b: 116, figs 18–22.

Leptoppia benyovszkyi: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Leptoppia benyovszkyi: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Leptoppia benyovszkyi: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

Leptoppia procera Mahunka, 1997

Leptoppia procera Mahunka, 1997a: 142, figs 41–43.

Leptoppia procera: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Leptoppia procera: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Leptoppia procera: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Leptoppia procera: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

OXYOPIIINAE Subías, 1989

Arcoppia Balogh, 1983

Arcoppia zsuzsankae (Mahunka, 2002)

Oxyoppiella zsuzsankae Mahunka, 2002a: 174, figs 13–16.

Oxyoppiella zsuzsankae: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Oxyoppiella (Oxyoppiella) zsuzsankae: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Arcoppia zsuzsankae: Subías 2021: 220.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. N of Andovoranto, between Artdombo and Andovoa (Mahunka 2002a); Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Fossoppia (Fossoppia) Mahunka, 1994

Fossoppia (Fossoppia) calcarata Mahunka, 1994

Fossoppia calcarata Mahunka, 1994: 81, figs 71–77.

Fossoppia calcarata: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Fossoppia calcarata: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Fossoppia calcarata: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Fossoppia calcarata: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Fossoppia (Fossoppia) calcarata: Subías 2017: 243.

Fossoppia calcarata: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

Fossoppia (Multifossoppia) Subías, 2017

Fossoppia (Multifossoppia) pirata
Mahunka, 1994

Fossoppia pirata Mahunka, 1994: 83, figs 78–81.

Fossoppia pirata: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Fossoppia pirata: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Fossoppia (Multifossoppia) pirata: Subías 2017: 244.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994).

Lineoppia Balogh & Balogh, 1983

Lineoppia tuberosa (Mahunka, 2009)

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppia) tuberosa Mahunka, 2009b: 56, figs 16–18.

Lineoppia tuberosa: Subías 2010: 238.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

Oxyoppia Balogh & Mahunka, 1969

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) Kulijev, 1978

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) pustulata
Mahunka, 1997

Oxyoppia pustulata Mahunka, 1997a: 144, figs 44–48.

Oxyoppia pustulata: Mahunka 2002a: 162

Oxyoppia pustulata: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Oxyoppia pustulata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 185, pl. 256, fig. 15., pl. 257, fig. 1.

Oxyoppiella (sic!) *punctulata* (sic!): Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Oxyoppia (Dzarogneta) pustulata: Subías 2004: 129.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Ile Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a); Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka 2011b).

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) Subías & Rodriguez, 1986

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) crassata
Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Oxyoppia (Oxyoppiella) crassata Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 44, figs 1a–1b.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Antongil Bay, Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

MYSTROPPIINAE Balogh, 1983

Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) Mahunka, 1986

Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) boraha
Mahunka, 1994

Brachioppiella boraha Mahunka, 1994: 57, figs 21–25.

Brachioppiella boraha: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Brachioppiella boraha: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Brachioppiella boraha: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Brachioppiella boraha: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 211, pl. 294, figs 9–10.

Rugoppia boraha: Mahunka 2009a: 110, figs 40–42.

Rugoppia boraha: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Brachioppiella (Brachioppiella) boraha: Subías 2019: 204.

Distribution. Madagascar and New Zealand.

Localities in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994, Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2010a).

Striatoppia Balogh, 1958

Striatoppia luisae Mahunka, 1994

Striatoppia luisae Mahunka, 1994: 76, figs 67–70.

Striatoppia luisiae (sic!): Mahunka 1997a: 120.

Striatoppia luisiae (sic!): Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Striatoppia luisae: Mahunka 2002b: 13.
Striatoppia luisae: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 185, pl. 257. figs 6–7.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994, Mahunka 1997a).

***Striatoppia madagascarensis* Balogh, 1961**

Striatoppia madagascarensis Balogh, 1961: 19, figs 18–19.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Balogh 1983: 32.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Subías & Balogh 1989: 388.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 185, pl. 257. figs 10–11.

Striatoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Distribution. Madagascar and Vietnam.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1960); Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

LANCEOPPIINAE Balogh, 1983

Lanceoppia (Baioppia) Luxton, 1985

***Lanceoppia (Baioppia) rugosa*
Ermilov & Starý, 2020**

Lanceoppia (Baioppia) rugosa Ermilov & Starý, 2020d: 703, fig. 3.

Lanceoppia (Baioppia) rugosa: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.

Lanceoppia (Baioppia) rugosa: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020d); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) Subías, 1989

***Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) cucheana*
Mahunka, 1994**

Lanceoppia cucheana Mahunka, 1994: 58, figs 26–32.

Lanceoppia cucheana: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) cucheana: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Lanceoppia cucheana: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 219, pl. 303. figs 5–6.

Aethioppia cucheana: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) cucheana: Subías 2004: 111.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Mananara North Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

***Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) kalalao*
Mahunka, 1997**

Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) kalalao Mahunka, 1997a: 135, figs 28–33.

Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) kalalao: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Lanceoppia (Bicristoppia) kalalao: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a).

New record. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W slope at 1–300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859).

Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) Hammer, 1962

***Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) madagascarensis*
Mahunka, 2002**

Lanceoppia madagascarensis Mahunka, 2002a: 171, figs 10–12.

Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Lanceoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Lanceoppia madagascarensis: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Lanceoppia madagascarensis: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 446.

Lanceoppia (Lanceoppia) madagascarensis: Subías 2004: 110.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2002a); Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka 2011b, Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Lanceoppia (Lancelalmoppia) Subías, 1989

***Lanceoppia (Lancelalmoppia) ravenala* (Mahunka, 1994)**

Radamoppia ravenala Mahunka, 1994: 68, figs. 47–55.

Radamoppia ravenata (sic!): Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Radamoppia ravenala: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Radamoppia ravenala: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 222, pl. 306. figs 11–12.

Lancelalmoppia ravenala: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Lancelalmoppia (Lancelalmoppia) ravenala: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Otoppia Balogh, 1983

***Otoppia midas* (Balogh, 1962)**

Oppia midas Balogh, 1962a: 133, figs 20–22.

Otoppia midas: Balogh 1983: 42, table 11 fig. 17-5.

Otoppia midas: Subías & Balogh 1989: 384.

Otoppia midas: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Otoppia midas: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Otoppia midas: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 215, pl. 298. figs 6–7.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Manjakandriana, La Mandraka (Balogh 1962a).

Pustuloppia Mahunka, 1994

***Pustuloppia madagassica* Mahunka, 1994**

Pustuloppia madagassica Mahunka, 1994: 66, figs 40–46.

Pustuloppia madagassica: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Pustuloppia madagassica: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Pustuloppia madagassica: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 224, pl. 309. figs 4–5.

Pustuloppia madagassica: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Setoppia Balogh, 1983

***Setoppia vanga* (Mahunka, 1994)**

Radamoppia vanga Mahunka, 1994: 70, figs 56–61.

Radamoppia vanga: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Radamoppia vanga: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Radamoppia vanga: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 218, pl. 302. figs 5–6.

Setoppia vanga: Subías 2004: 112.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1994).

Trematoppia Balogh, 1962

***Trematoppia cristipes* Balogh, 1962**

Trematoppia cristipes Balogh, 1962a: 135, figs 23–25.

Trematoppia cristipes: Balogh 1983: 40, table 10 fig. 17–1.

Trematoppia cristipes: Subías & Balogh 1989: 389.

Trematoppia cristipes: Mahunka 1997a: 120.

Trematoppia cristipes: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Trematoppia cristipes: Mahunka 2002b: 13, figs 13–16.

Trematoppia cristipes: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 221, pl. 306. figs 7–8.

Trematoppia cristipes: Mahunka 2011a: 7, figs 13–16.

Trematoppia cristipes: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Madagascar and Mexico.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1962a); Montagne d'Ambre National Park, Island of Nosy Be Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a); Ranomafana (Mahunka 2011a).

MEDIOPPIINAE Subías & Mínguez, 1985

***Micropia* Balogh, 1983**

***Micropia minus* (Paoli, 1908)**

Damaeosoma minus Paoli, 1908: 48, pl. 3. fig. 11.
Micropia minus: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

MULTIOPPIINAE Balogh, 1983

***Multioppia (Hammeroppia)*
Vasilu & Ivan, 2009**

***Multioppia (Hammeroppia) wilsoni* Aoki, 1964**

Multioppia wilsoni Aoki, 1964: 652, figs 6–8.
Multioppia (Hammeroppia) wilsoni: Ermilov & Starý, 2020d: 705.
Multioppia (Hammeroppia) wilsoni: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.
Multioppia (Hammeroppia) wilsoni: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan except the Antarctic region.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020d); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia)* Subías, 1980**

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) alata*
(Mahunka, 1997)**

Sphagnoppia alata Mahunka, 1997a: 147, figs 49–53.
Sphagnoppia alata: Mahunka 2002a: 162.
Sphagnoppia alata: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Sphagnoppia alata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 226, pl. 311. fig. 13–14.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) alata: Subías 2004: 118.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a).

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) lata*
Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012**

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) lata Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 47, figs 3a–3d.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) lata: Ermilov & Starý 2020i: 447.

Distribution: Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mananara North Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012); Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020i).

Remarks. During collection research we recognized that the label in the vial refers to a different locality than the published one; holotype and one paratype: Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W slope at 1–300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859). Even in the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka this locality is connected to the holotype. From the published holotype locality we found just another paratype: Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and Pandanus ssp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921).

***Ramusella (Insculptoppiella)*
Subías & Rodríguez, 1986**

***Ramusella (Insculptoppia) aepyornis*
Mahunka, 1994**

Ramusella aepyornis Mahunka, 1994: 74, figs 62–66.
Ramusella aepyornis: Mahunka 2002a: 162.
Ramusella aepyornis: Mahunka 2002b: 13.
Ramusella aepyornis (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 207, pl. 288. fig. 15., pl. 289. fig. 1.

Ramusella (Insculptoppiella) aepyornis: Subías 2004: 119.

Ramusella (Insculptoppia) aepyornis: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: 53 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1994); 73 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 2009c).

Ramusella (Ramusella) Hammer, 1962

Ramusella (Ramusella) arcuata

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Ramusella (Ramusella) arcuata Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 45, figs 2a–2c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Mananara North Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Ramusella (Ramusella) clavipectinata

(Michael, 1885)

Notaspis clavipectinata Michael, 1885: 395, pl. 7. fig. 6.

Ramusella (Ramusella) clavipectinata: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Ramusella clavipectinata: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 243.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan (Palearctic: frequent, U.S.A.: California, furthermore Madagascar, Oriental and Hawaii).

Locality in Madagascar: Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

Ramuselloppia Subías & Rodríguez, 1986

Ramuselloppia indistincta Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Ramuselloppia indistincta Ermilov & Starý, 2020d: 689, figs 1–2.

Ramuselloppia indistincta: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020d).

OPPIELLINAE Seniczak, 1975

Berniniella (Berniniella) Balogh, 1983

Berniniella (Berniniella) bicarinata (Paoli, 1908)

Dameosoma bicarinatum Paoli, 1908: 59, fig. 4: 21.

Berniniella bicarinata: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Berniniella (Berniniella) bicarinata: Subías 2004: 125.

Distribution. Palearctic region, Madagascar and Vietnam.

Locality in Madagascar: Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Elaphoppia Balogh, 1983

Elaphoppia quadripilosa (Balogh, 1960)

Oppia quadripilosa Balogh, 1960: 18, figs 16–17.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Balogh 1983: 24, table 3, figs 9–5.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Subías & Balogh 1989: 377.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Mahunka 1997a: 119.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Elaphoppia quadripilosa: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 188, pl. 262. figs 1–2.

Distribution. Madagascar and Vietnam.

Localities in Madagascar: Manjahandriana, Ambotolaona (Balogh 1960); Ile de Nosy Boraha (Mahunka 1997a).

Oppiella Jacot, 1937

Oppiella nova (Oudemans, 1902)

Eremaeus novus Oudemans, 1902: 36.

Oppiella nova: Mahunka 1997a: 120.

Oppiella nova: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Oppiella nova: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Oppiella nova: Mahunka 2009c: 339.

Oppiella nova: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Oppiella (Oppiella) nova: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Oppiella nova: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan.

Localities in Madagascar: Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 1997a, Mahunka 2009c); Andasibe (Perinet) (Mahunka 2011b); Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka 2011b, Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

QUADROPPIIDAE Balogh, 1983

Quadroppia (Coronoquadroppia) Balogh, 1983

Quadroppia (Coronoquadroppia) circumita (Hammer, 1961)

Oppia circumita Hammer, 1961: 48, fig. 39.

Quadroppia circumita: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 48, figs 4a–4b.

Quadroppia (Coronoquadroppia) circumita: Subías 2004: 113.

Distribution. Pantropical and subtropical.

Locality in Madagascar: Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

TRIZETOIDEA Ewing, 1917

NOSYBELBIDAE Mahunka, 1994

Nosybelba Mahunka, 1994

Nosybelba oppiana Mahunka, 1994

Nosybelba oppiana Mahunka, 1994: 86, figs 82–90.

Nosybelba oppiana: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Nosybelba oppiana: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Nosybea (sic!) *oppiana:* Balogh & Balogh 2002: 194, pl. 270, figs 6–7.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Analamazoatra Special Reserve (Mahunka 1994).

Nosybelba spinipes (Balogh, 1962)

Oppia spinipes Balogh, 1962a: 131, figs 16–19.

Aethioppia spinipes: Balogh 1983: 54.

Aethioppia spinipes: Subías & Balogh 1989: 373.

Aethioppia spinipes: Mahunka 2002a: 162.

Aethioppia spinipes: Mahunka 2002b: 12.

Nosybelba spinipes: Subías 2014: 201.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Manjakandriana, La Mandraka (Balogh 1962a).

SUCTOBELBIDAE JACOT, 1938

Interbelba Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Interbelba solifera

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Interbelba solifera Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 48, figs 5a–5b.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Antongil Bay, Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) Chinone, 2003

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) bercziki (Mahunka, 2009)

Madabelba bercziki Mahunka, 2009b: 58, figs 19–21.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) bercziki: Subías 2017: 259.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) duplicondyla (Mahunka, 2009)

Suctobelbella duplicondyla Mahunka, 2009a: 113, figs 46–49.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) duplicondyla: Subías 2017: 259.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) madegassica (Mahunka, 2011)

Neosuctobelba madegassica Mahunka, 2011a: 9, figs 17–20.

Novosuctobelba (Leptosuctobelba) madegassica: Subías 2017: 259.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

***Parasuctobelba* Hammer, 1977**

Parasuctobelba subcomplexa

(Balogh & Mahunka, 1968)

Suctobelba subcomplexa Balogh & Mahunka, 1968: 328, fig. 18.

Parasuctobelba subcomplexa: Subías 2009: 247.

Distribution. Pantropical: Neotropical, Oriental (Borneo), Ethiopian (Guinea Ecuatorial: I. Bioko [Fernando Poo] and Kenya) and Hawaii.

New record. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

Remarks. New to the fauna of Madagascar.

***Parasuctobelba vohimana* Mahunka, 2009**

Parasuctobelba vohimana Mahunka 2009a: 110, figs 43–45.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

***Persuctobelba* Mahunka, 2001**

***Persuctobelba divisa* Mahunka, 2001**

Persuctobelba divisa Mahunka, 2001: 278, figs 1–4.

Persuctobelba divisa: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar

Localities in Madagascar. Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park, Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2001).

New record. Ambohitantely Forest Reserve, E of Manonkazo village (Ankaszabz town). Relic

xerophyllous (dry evergreen) plateau forest at 1500–1530 m alt. 05–06.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9444) (Afr-857).

Persuctobelba flagellatissima

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Persuctobelba flagellatissima Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 50, figs 6a–6c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Antongil Bay, Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

***Persuctobelba monster* Mahunka, 2001**

Persuctobelba monster Mahunka, 2001: 281, figs 5–8.

Persuctobelba monster: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Persuctobelba monster: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. between Ambato-laona and Mandraka (Mahunka 2001); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) Ryabinin, 1975

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) spirochaeta

Mahunka, 1983

Suctobelbella spirochaeta Mahunka, 1983c: 425, figs 84–88.

Suctobelbella spirochaeta: Mahunka 2009a: 91.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) spirochaeta: Ermilov, Shtanchaeva & Subías 2014: 1594.

Distribution. Ethiopian and Japan.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) variosetosa

(Hammer, 1961)

Suctobelba variosetosa Hammer, 1961: 43, fig. 35.

Discosuctobelba variosetosa: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012: 44.

Suctobelbella (Ussuribata) variosetosa: Ermilov, Shtanchaeva & Subías 2014: 1595.

Distribution. Pantropical (frequent) and Japan.

Locality in Madagascar. Masoala Peninsula (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Remarks. During collection research we recognized that the label in the vial refers to a different locality than the published one: Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antani-naomby summit with tree ferns and with Marattia fraxinea, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29.07.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917). Even in the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka this locality is connected to the species.

***Suctobelbilla* Jacot, 1938**

Suctobelbilla punctocostulata

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Suctobelbilla punctocostulata Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 51, figs 7a–7c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Antongil Bay, Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

Suctobelbilla tumida

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012

Suctobelbilla tumida Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2012: 53, figs 8a–8c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Mangabe Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2012).

TECTOCEPHEOIDEA Grandjean, 1954

TECTOCEPHEIDAE Grandjean, 1954

***Tectocepheus* Berlese, 1896**

***Tectocepheus minor* Berlese, 1903**

Tectocepheus minor Berlese, 1903: 252.

Tectocepheus minor: Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011: 126.

Distribution. Semicosmopolitan: Central and South Europe, East Asia, tropical.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

***Tectocepheus velatus velatus* (Michael, 1880)**

Tegeocranus velatus Michael, 1880: 190, pl. 6. figs 6–9.

Tectocepheus velatus velatus: Mahunka 2009c: 347.

Tectocepheus velatus velatus: Schabetsberger et al. 2013: 331.

Tectocepheus velatus velatus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Cosmopolitan.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c); Amber Mountains National Park (Schabetsberger et al. 2013).

LIMNOZETOIDEA Thor, 1937

AUSTRACHTERIIDAE Luxton, 1985

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) Hammer, 1958

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) cuneatus

Mahunka, 2010

Lamellobates cuneatus Mahunka, 2010a: 54, figs 23–25.

Lamellobates (Lamellobates) cuneatus: Subías 2010: 321.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2010a).

AMERONOTHROIDEA Willmann, 1931

TEGEOCRANELLIDAE P. Balogh, 1987

***Tegeocranellus* Berlese, 1913**

***Tegeocranellus hungarorum* Mahunka, 2009**

Tegeocranellus hungarorum Mahunka, 2009a: 96, figs 12–14.

Tegeocranellus hungarorum: Mahunka 2011: 2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a); Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka 2011a).

CYMBAEREMAEOIDEA Sellnick, 1928

CYMBAEREMAEIDAE Sellnick, 1928

***Scapheremaeus* Berlese, 1910**

***Scapheremaeus anteriorugosus* Mahunka, 2011**

Scapheremaeus anteriorugosus Mahunka, 2011a: 11, figs 21–23.

Scapheremaeus anteriorugosus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022b: 809.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Mount Maromizaha south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2011a); Ankaratra Mount (Ermilov & Frolov 2022b).

Scapheremaeus pauliani

Fernandez & Cleva, 2010

Scapheremaeus pauliani Fernandez & Cleva, 2010a: 103, figs 1–6.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Anosyenne Mountains (Fernandez & Cleva 2010a).

EREMAEOZETOIDEA Piffel, 1972

EREMAEOZETIDAE Piffel, 1972

***Idiozetes* Aoki, 1976**

Idiozetes malgache

Fernandez, Cleva & Theron, 2010

Idiozetes malgache Fernandez, Cleva & Theron, 2010: 438, figs 1–40.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Antongil Bay, Nosy Mangabe Island (Fernandez, Cleva & Theron 2010).

***Rogerzetes* Fernandez, Theron & Cleva, 2011**

***Rogerzetes betschi* (Fernandez & Cleva, 2009)**

Eremaozetes betschi Fernandez & Cleva, 2009: 70, figs 1–8.

Eremaozetes betschi: Mahunka 2011a: 3.

Rogerzetes betschi: Fernandez, Theron & Cleva 2011: 69, fig. 7.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Ankarongambe forest (10 km E/SE Ambohidray) (Fernandez & Cleva 2009); Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park (Mahunka 2011a).

Rogerzetes lacouturieri

Fernandez, Theron & Cleva, 2011

Rogerzetes lacouturieri Fernandez, Theron & Cleva, 2011: 62, figs 1–24.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar: Manankaza Forest Station, Ambohitantely (Fernandez, Theron & Cleva 2011).

LICNEREMAEOIDEA Grandjean, 1931

EREMELLIDAE Balogh, 1961

***Afreremella* (*Arboreremella*)**

Ermilov & Frolov, 2022

Afreremella* (*Arboreremella*) *madagascarensis

Ermilov & Frolov, 2022

Afreremella (*Arboreremella*) *madagascarensis* Ermilov & Frolov, 2022b: 800, figs 1–3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar: Ankaratra Mount (Ermilov & Frolov 2022b).

***Eremella* Berlese, 1913**

***Eremella* (*Eremella*) *induta* Berlese, 1913**

Eremella induta Berlese, 1913: 97.

Eremella induta: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Eremella (*Eremella*) *induta*: Subías 2020: 290.

Distribution. Pantropical and Subtropical.

Locality in Madagascar: Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka 2011b).

Eremella (Licnocepheus) simpliseta
(Mahunka, 2011)

Triteremella simpliseta Mahunka, 2011b: 54, figs 8a–c.
Eremella simpliseta: Ermilov & Frolov 2019: 223.
Eremella (Licnocepheus) simpliseta: Subías 2020: 290.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Peyrieras, Causse de Kelifelly (Mahunka 2011b).

LAMELLAREIDAE Balogh, 1972

Microlamellarea Coetzee, 1987

Microlamellarea coetzeae
Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Microlamellarea coetzeae Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 136, figs 7a–b.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

LICNEREMAEIDAE Grandjean, 1931

Licneremaeus Paoli, 1908

Licneremaeus polygonalis Hammer, 1971

Licneremaeus polygonalis Hammer, 1971: 29, pl. 18–19, fig. 31a–b.

Licneremaeus polygonatus (sic!): Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011: 126.

Distribution. Pacific Islands, Vietnam and Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

PASSALOZETIDAE Grandjean, 1954

Bipassalozetes (Passalobates)
Pérez-Íñigo & Peña, 1996

Bipassalozetes (Passalobates) berndhauseri
(Mahunka, 1997)

Passalozetes (Bipassalozetes) berndhauseri Mahunka, 1997a: 153–156.

Passalozetes (Bipassalozetes) hauseri (sic!) Mahunka, 1997a: figs 65–68.

Passalozetes (Bipassalozetes) berndhauseri: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Passalozetes hauseri: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 264, pl. 365, figs 7–8.

Bipassalozetes (Passalobates) berndhauseri: Subías 2017: 327.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a).

Passalozetes (Passalozetes) Grandjean, 1932

Passalozetes (Passalozetes) lienhardi
Mahunka, 1997

Passalozetes (Passalozetes) lienhardi Mahunka, 1997a: 153, figs 61–64.

Passalozetes (Passalozetes) lienhardi: Mahunka 2002b: 13.

Passalozetes lienhardi: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 264, pl. 365, figs 9–10.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. 45 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary, 53 km from Tôlanaro on the road to Amboasary (Mahunka 1997a).

PHENOPELOPOIDEA Petrunkevich, 1955

PHENOPELOPIDAE Petrunkevich, 1955

Eupelops Ewing, 1917

Eupelops costulatus Mahunka, 2011

Eupelops costulatus Mahunka, 2011b: 56, figs 9a–d.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011b).

ACHIPTERIOIDEA Thor, 1929

TEGORIBATIDAE Grandjean, 1954

***Lemurobates* Mahunka, 1997**

***Lemurobates antsiranana* Mahunka, 1997**

Lemurobates antsiranana Mahunka, 1997a: 159, figs 75–81.

Lemurobates antsiranana: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Lemurobates antsiranana (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 333, pl. 442. figs 2–3.

Lemurobates antsiranana: Mahunka 2010a: 48.

Lemurobates antsiranana: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park; Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a); Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park, Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2010a).

New record. Toamasina Prov. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the NW slope of Behafotra Hill, at 250–300 m alt., with 3500 mm annual rainfall. 16°27.1-3'S, 49°47.6'E, 14–15.08.1998, Leg. T. Pócs (No. 9877) (Afr-920).

ORIBATELLOIDEA Jacot, 1925

ORIBATELLIDAE Jacot, 1925

***Oribatella* (*Oribatella*) Banks, 1895**

***Oribatella* (*Oribatella*) *madagascarensis*
Mahunka, 1997**

Oribatella madagascarensis Mahunka, 1997a: 156, figs 69–74.

Oribatella madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Oribatella madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 298, pl. 404. figs 3–4.

Oribatella (*Oribatella*) *madagascarensis*: Subías 2004: 171.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Island of Nosy Be, Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

ORIPODOIDEA Jacot, 1925

CALOPPIIDAE Balogh, 1961

***Zetorchella* Berlese, 1916**

***Zetorchella semirugosa* (Mahunka, 2011)**

Chaunoproctus semirugosus Mahunka, 2011b: 60, figs 11a–d.

Zetorchella semirugosa: Subías 2012: 385.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka 2011b).

HAPLOZETIDAE Grandjean, 1936

***Indoribates* (*Haplozetes*) Willmann, 1935**

***Indoribates* (*Haplozetes*) *madagascarensis*
(Balogh, 1960)**

Scheloribates madagascarensis Balogh, 1960: 25, figs 30–31.

Scheloribates madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Indoribates (*Haplozetes*) *madagascarensis*: Subías 2017: 440.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Locality in Madagascar. Nosy Be, Pointe a la Fievre (Balogh 1960).

***Indoribates* (*Indoribates*) Jacot, 1929**

***Indoribates* (*Indoribates*) *olszanowskii*
Ermilov & Starý, 2020**

Indoribates olszanowskii Ermilov & Starý, 2020k: 362, figs 1–7.

Indoribates (*Indoribates*) *olszanowskii*: Subías 2021: 400.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020k).

Peloribates (Peloribates) Berlese, 1908

Peloribates (Peloribates) pocsi

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Peloribates (Peloribates) pocsi Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 138, figs 9a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ambohitantely Forest Reserve (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) Mahunka, 2011

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) incompatibilis

Mahunka, 2011

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) incompatibilis Mahunka, 2011b: 62, figs 12a–d.

Distribution. Ethiopian, Holarctic and Neotropical.

Locality in Madagascar. Peyrieras, Causse de Kelifelly (Mahunka 2011b).

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) montagnensis

Ermilov & Starý, 2020.

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) montagnensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020e: 146, figs 1–3.

Peloribates (Peloribatodes) montagnensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020e).

Pilobatella (Pilobatella)

Balogh & Mahunka, 1967

***Pilobatella (Pilobatella) brevipila* Mahunka, 2011**

Pilobatella brevipila Mahunka, 2011a: 13, figs 24–27.

Pilobatella (Pilobatella) brevipila: Subías 2017: 447.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

Pilobatella (Pilobatella) kovaci

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Pilobatella kovaci Ermilov & Starý, 2020g: 550, fig. 4.

Pilobatella (Pilobatella) kovaci: Subías 2021: 406.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020g).

Pilobatella (Pilobatella) mikoi

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Pilobatella mikoi Ermilov & Starý, 2020g: 547, figs 1–3.

Pilobatella (Pilobatella) mikoi: Subías 2021: 406.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020g).

Pilobates (Pilobates) Balogh, 1960

Pilobates (Pilobates) africanus

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Pilobates africanus Ermilov & Starý, 2020e: 150, figs 4–6.

Pilobates (Pilobates) africanus: Subías 2021: 407.

Pilobates africanus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020e).

Pilobates (Pilobates) longiprocessus

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Pilobates longiprocessus Ermilov & Starý, 2020j: 124, figs 1–7.

Pilobates (Pilobates) longiprocessus: Subías 2021: 407.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020j).

***Pilobates (Pilobates) parastaryi* Ermilov, 2020**

Pilobates parastaryi Ermilov, 2020: 1325, fig. 4.

Pilobates (Pilobates) parastaryi: Subías 2021: 407.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov 2020).

***Pilobates (Pilobates) staryi* Ermilov, 2020**

Pilobates staryi Ermilov, 2020: 1321, figs 1–3.

Pilobates (Pilobates) staryi: Subías 2021: 407.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov 2020).

Protoribates (Triaunguis) Kulijev, 1978

Protoribates (Triaunguis) ziemowiti

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Protoribates ziemowiti Ermilov & Starý, 2020k: 365, figs 8–14.

Protoribates (Triaunguis) ziemowiti: Subías 2021: 397.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020k).

Rostrozetes Sellnick, 1925

***Rostrozetes poensis* (Mihelčič, 1957)**

Carabozetes poensis Mihelčič, 1957: 64, fig. 10.

Rostrozetes pulcherrimus Balogh, 1960: 29, fig. 35.

Trachyoribates (Rostrozetes) pulcherrimus: Mahunka 2009a: 120.

Rostrozetes pulcherrimus: Mahunka 2011a: 3.

Rostrozetes poensis: Subías 2021: 408.

Distribution. Pantropical (frequent) and subtropical.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjakandriana, La Mandraka (Balogh 1960); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a, Mahunka 2011a).

Vilhenabates Balogh, 1963

***Vilhenabates ambohitra* Mahunka, 2009**

Vilhenabates ambohitra Mahunka, 2009c: 348, figs 17–19.

Vilhenabates ambohitra: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

***Vilhenabates dissecatus* Mahunka, 2009**

Vilhenabates dissecatus Mahunka, 2009a: 118, figs 53–56.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009a).

ORBATULIDAE Thor, 1929

Lucoppia Berlese, 1908

***Lucoppia ankaratraensis* Ermilov & Frolov, 2022**

Lucoppia ankaratraensis Ermilov & Frolov, 2022b: 804, figs 4–6.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankaratra Mount (Ermilov & Frolov 2022b).

PARAKALUMMIDAE Grandjean, 1936

Neoribates (Neoribates) Berlese, 1914

Neoribates (Neoribates) africanus

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Neoribates (Neoribates) africanus Ermilov & Starý, 2020b: 115, figs 1–3.

Neoribates africanus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020b).

Neoribates (Neoribates) madagascarensis

Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Neoribates (Neoribates) madagascarensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020b: 119, figs 4–6.

Neoribates madagascarensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020b).

ORIPODIDAE JACOT, 1925

***Oripoda* Banks, 1904**

***Oripoda attenuata* Mahunka, 2011**

Oripoda attenuata Mahunka, 2011b: 58, figs 10a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mangabé Island, Antongil Bay (Mahunka 2011b).

***Oripoda auriculata* Mahunka, 1996**

Oripoda auriculata Mahunka, 1996b: 118, figs 23–25.

Oripoda auriculata: Balogh & Balogh 1999b: 35, figs 76–77.

Oripoda auriculata: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Oripoda auriculata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 311, pl. 421, figs 3–4.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b).

***Protoripoda (Protoripoda)* Balogh, 1970**

***Protoripoda (Protoripoda) nasuta*
Mahunka, 2009**

Protoripoda nasuta Mahunka, 2009b: 58, figs 22–23.

Protoripoda (Protoripoda) nasuta: Subías 2010: 398.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b).

***Pseudopirnodus* Baranek, 1985**

***Pseudopirnodus madegassus* Mahunka, 1996**

Pseudopirnodus madegassus Mahunka, 1996b: 122, figs 26–29.

Pseudopirnodus madegassus: Balogh & Balogh 1999b: 43, figs 124–125.

Pseudopirnodus madegassus: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Pseudopirnodus madegassus: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 308, pl. 416, figs 4–5.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996b).

SCHELORIBATIDAE Grandjean, 1933

***Euscheloribates* Kunst, 1958**

***Euscheloribates translamellatus*
(Mahunka, 2009)**

Ambrobates translamellatus Mahunka, 2009c: 348, figs 14–16.

Euscheloribates translamellatus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2009c).

***Heteroleius* Balogh & Mahunka, 1966**

***Heteroleius flagellifer*
Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011**

Heteroleius flagellifer Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 141, figs 10a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Analamazoatra Special Reserve, Antsiranana Province, Nosy Komba Island (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

Remarks. According to the original description the holotype and 4 paratypes are deposited in Geneva (MHNG) and 3 paratypes are in Budapest (HNHM). However, in the HNHM collection we found two vials: one is labelled as holotype Nosy Mangabe Island in Antongil Bay S of Maroantsetra town. Mesic lowland rainforest on the W slope at 1–300 m alt. 15°29'S, 49°45'E, 13.09.1994, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9450) (Afr-859) and one is labelled as paratype with 5 specimens (same locality as the holotype). We checked Mahunka's handwritten notebook but we found no helpful information there.

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) Berlese, 1908

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) mahnerti

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2008

Scheloribates mahnerti Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2008: 84, figs 21–23.

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) mahnerti: Subías 2009: 384.

Scheloribates mahnerti: Mahunka 2011b: 44.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Locality in Madagascar. Mangabé Island, Antongil Bay (Mahunka 2011b).

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) striolatus

Balogh, 1960

Scheloribates striolatus Balogh, 1960: 27, figs 32–34.

Scheloribates striolatus: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Scheloribates (Scheloribates) striolatus: Subías 2004: 202.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Manjakandriana, Ambotolaona (Balogh 1960).

Tuberemaeus Sellnick, 1930

Tuberemaeus puruczkyi

Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011

Tuberemaeus puruczkyi Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 143, figs 11a–c.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

CERATOZETOIDEA Jacot, 1925

HUMEROBATIDAE Grandjean, 1970

***Antarctozetes* Balogh, 1961**

Antarctozetes nasalis

(Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011)

Africoribates nasalis Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 2011: 137, figs 8a–c.

Antarctozetes nasalis: Subías 2019: 339.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Antsiranana Province, Nosy Komba Island, Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp 2011).

Remarks. During collection research we recognised that the label in the vial refers to a different locality than the published one: Toamasina Province. Maromizaha forest. Mossy montane rainforest with bamboo (*Nastus* sp.) undergrowth on the summit ridge of Mount Maromizaha, south of the Andasibe National Park and the Antananarivo Toamasina road, 2 km W of Anevoka village, at 1080–1214 m alt. 18°57.8'S, 48°27.5'E, 26.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9890) (Afr-923). Even in the handwritten notebook of Sándor Mahunka this locality is connected to the species and not the published one.

***Humerobates* Sellnick, 1928**

***Humerobates africanus* (Mahunka, 1984)**

Baloghobates africanus Mahunka, 1984: 118, figs 21 A–E.

Humerobates africanus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022b: 809.

Distribution. Afrotropical region.

Locality in Madagascar. Ankaratra Mount Ermilov & Frolov 2022b).

PUNCTORIBATIDAE Thor, 1937

***Punctoribates* Berlese, 1908**

***Punctoribates longiporosus* Balogh, 1963**

Punctoribates longiporosus Balogh, 1963: 41, figs 12–13.

Punctoribates (Minguezetes) longiporosus: Subías 2008: 346.

Punctoribates longiporosus: Mahunka 2011a: 3.

Punctoribates longiporosus: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Ethiopian, Oriental, Northeast China, Mexico.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Mahunka 2011a).

GALUMNOIDEA Jacot, 1925

GALUMNELLIDAE Balogh, 1961

Galumnella (Galumnella) Berlese, 1916

***Galumnella (Galumnella) pauliani* Balogh, 1960**

Galumnella pauliani Balogh, 1960: 36, fig. 45.
Galumnella pauliani: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 361, pl. 475, fig. 8.
Galumnella pauliani: Mahunka 2002b: 15.
Galumnella (Galumnella) pauliani: Subías 2004: 222.

Distribution. Madagascar and Vietnam.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1960).

New record. Toamasina Prov., Mananara Nord Biosphere Reserve and National Park. Lowland rainforest on the E slopes of Mahavoho Hill (very wet types along Manahovo River, with many tree ferns, palms and *Pandanus* spp., less humid on slopes) at 220–300 m alt. 16°27'S, 49°46.9–47.5'E, 14–15.08.1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9878) (Afr-921).

GALUMNIDAE JACOT, 1925

Allogalumna (Acroalumna) Grandjean, 1956

***Allogalumna (Acroalumna) costata*
Mahunka, 1996**

Allogalumna costata Mahunka, 1996c: 164, figs 1–5.
Allogalumna costata: Mahunka 2002b: 14.
Allogalumna costata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 382, pl. 498, figs 3–4.
Allogalumna costata: Mahunka 2011a: 3.
Allogalumna (Acroalumna) costata: Subías 2021: 412.

Distribution. Madagascar and Vietnam.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

***Allogalumna (Acroalumna) superporosa*
Mahunka, 1996**

Allogalumna superporosa Mahunka, 1996c: 169, figs 16–18.

Allogalumna superporosa: Mahunka 2002b: 14.
Allogalumna superporosa: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 382, pl. 498, figs 6–7.
Allogalumna (Acroalumna) superporosa: Subías 2021: 413.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) Grandjean, 1936

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) insolita*
Mahunka, 1996**

Allogalumna insolita Mahunka, 1996c: 164, figs 6–10.
Allogalumna insolita: Mahunka 2002b: 14.
Allogalumna insolita: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 382, pl. 498, fig. 1.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) insolita: Subías 2019: 404.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) longula*
Balogh, 1960**

Xenogalumna longula Balogh, 1960: 32, figs 39–41.
Xenogalumna longula: Mahunka 2002b: 15.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) longula: Ermilov & Klimov 2017: 55.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1960).

***Allogalumna (Allogalumna) madagascarensis*
(Balogh, 1960)**

Ctenogalumna madagascarensis Balogh, 1960: 34, figs 42–44.
Allogalumna madagascarensis: Mahunka 1996c: 168, figs 11–12.
Allogalumna madagascarensis: Mahunka 2002b: 14.
Ctenogalumna madagascarensis: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 380, pl. 495, fig. 10.
Allogalumna (Allogalumna) madagascarensis: Subías 2019: 404.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Mont Papango near Befotaka (Balogh 1960); Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) paramadagascarensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Allogalumna paramadagascarensis Ermilov & Starý, 2020f: 100, figs 1–4.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) paramadagascarensis: Subías 2021: 412.

Allogalumna paramadagascarensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 443.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020f).

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) paravojnitsi Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Allogalumna paravojnitsi Ermilov & Starý, 2020f: 105, figs 1–4.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) paravojnitsi: Subías 2021: 412.

Allogalumna paravojnitsi: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 243.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020f).

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) pocsi Mahunka, 1996

Allogalumna pocsi Mahunka, 1996c: 169, figs 13–15.

Allogalumna pocsi: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Allogalumna pocsi: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 382, pl. 498, fig. 9., pl. 499, fig. 1.

Allogalumna (Allogalumna) pocsi: Subías 2021: 415.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

Angulogalumna Grishina, 1981

Angulogalumna grishinae Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Angulogalumna grishinae Ermilov & Starý, 2020l: 67, figs 1–4.

Angulogalumna grishinae: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020l, Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

Galumna (Galumna) Heyden, 1826

Galumna (Galumna) ankaratra Mahunka, 1997

Galumna ankaratra Mahunka, 1997a: 162, figs 82–85.

Galumna ankaratra: Mahunka 2002b: 14.

Galumna ankarata (sic!): Balogh & Balogh 2002: 369, pl. 483, fig. 10.

Galumna ankaratra (sic!): Mahunka 2011a: 3.

Galumna (Galumna) ankaratra: Subías 2004: 214.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Manjakatombo Forest Station (Mahunka 1997a); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

Galumna (Galumna) armatifera Mahunka, 1996

Galumna armatifera Mahunka, 1996c: 172, figs 19–22.

Galumna armatifera: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Galumna armatifera: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 369, pl. 483, figs 8–9.

Galumna armatifera: Mahunka 2009b: 48.

Galumna armatifera: Mahunka 2011a: 3.

Galumna armatifera: Ermilov & Starý 2020a.

Galumna armatifera: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Galumna (Galumna) armatifera: Subías 2004: 214.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Masoala peninsula, Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c); Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2009b, Mahunka 2011a); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Galumna (Galumna) brevilineata Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Galumna (Galumna) brevilineata Ermilov & Starý, 2020h: 1385, figs 1–3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020h).

Galumna (Galumna) engelbrechti
Mahunka, 1997

Galumna engelbrechti Mahunka, 1997a: 162, figs 86–90.

Galumna engelbrechti: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Galumna engelbrechti: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 369, pl. 483. fig. 11.

Galumna (Galumna) engelbrechti: Subías 2004: 215.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

Galumna (Galumna) granalata Aoki, 1984

Galumna granalata Aoki, 1984: 146, fig. 23.

Galumna (Galumna) granalata: Subías 2004: 215.

Galumna granalata: Ermilov & Starý 2020a: 73.

Galumna granalata: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Oriental region and Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Galumna (Galumna) janosbaloghi
Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Galumna (Galumna) janosbaloghi Ermilov & Starý, 2020a: 68, figs 4–6.

Galumna janosbaloghi: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Galumna (Galumna) montagnensis
Ermilov & Frolov, 2022

Galumna (Galumna) montagnensis Ermilov & Frolov, 2022a: 445, fig. 3.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

Galumna (Galumna) paraarmatifera
Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Galumna (Galumna) paraarmatifera Ermilov & Starý, 2020h: 1389, figs 4–5.

Galumna paraarmatifera: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Andasibe-Mantadia National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020h); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

Galumna (Galumna) sandormahunkai
Ermilov & Starý, 2020

Galumna (Galumna) sandormahunkai Ermilov & Starý, 2020a: 65, figs 1–3.

Galumna sandormahunkai: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Galumna (Galumna) tuberculata Mahunka, 1997

Galumna tuberculata Mahunka, 1997a: 167, figs 91–95.

Galumna tuberculata: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Galumna tuberculata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 369, pl. 483. figs 5–6.

Galumna (Galumna) tuberculata: Subías 2004: 217.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Lokobe Strict Nature Reserve (Mahunka 1997a).

New record. Antsiranana Prov. Nosy Komba Island. Submontane rainforest remnants in the NW valley of Antaninaomby summit with tree ferns and with *Marattia fraxinea*, at 570–580 m alt. 13°23.2'S, 48°20.8'E, 29. 07. 1998, leg. T. Pócs (No. 9862) (Afr-917).

Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) Balogh, 1960

***Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) reducta*
Mahunka, 1996**

Leptogalumna reducta Mahunka, 1996c: 174, figs 23–26.

Leptogalumna reducta: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Leptogalumna (Leptogalumna) reducta: Subías 2015: 455.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

Orthogalumna Balogh, 1960

***Orthogalumna saeva* Balogh, 1960**

Orthogalumna saeva Balogh, 1960: 31, figs 36–38.

Orthogalumna saeva: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 374, pl. 488, fig. 6.

Orthogalumna saeva: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Distribution. Ethiopian, Oriental (Indian: Tripura, and south-eastern China, Okinawa), Neotropical (Lesser Antilles).

Locality in Madagascar. Ile Tromelin (Balogh 1960).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) Grandjean, 1936

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) amamiensis*
Aoki, 1984**

Pergalumna amamiensis Aoki, 1984: 146, fig. 24.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) amamiensis: Subías 2016: 460.

Pergalumna amamiensis: Ermilov & Starý 2020a: 73.

Pergalumna amamiensis: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Ethiopian region and Japan.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) ambrensis* Ermilov & Frolov, 2022**

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) ambrensis Ermilov & Frolov, 2022a: 444, figs 1–2.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) andasibe*
Mahunka, 1996**

Pergalumna andasibe Mahunka, 1996c: 175, figs 27–29.

Pergalumna andasibe: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Pergalumna andasibe: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 377, pl. 492, fig. 8.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) andasibe: Subías 2016: 460.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) bicristata*
Mahunka, 2011**

Pergalumna bicristata Mahunka, 2011a: 16, figs 32–34.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) bicristata: Subías 2016: 460.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) conspicua*
Balogh, 1962**

Pergalumna conspicua Balogh, 1962c: 119, figs 59–60.

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) conspicua: Subías 2016: 461.

Pergalumna conspicua: Ermilov & Starý 2020a: 73.

Pergalumna conspicua: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Ethiopian region.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

***Pergalumna (Pergalumna) fastigata*
Mahunka, 1996**

Pergalumna fastigata Mahunka, 1996c: 177, figs 30–33.

Pergalumna fastigata: Mahunka 2002b: 15.
Pergalumna fastigata: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 379, pl. 495, fig. 9.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) fascigata: Subías 2016: 461.
Pergalumna fastigata: Ermilov & Starý 2020a: 73.
Pergalumna fastigata: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Localities in Madagascar. Masoala peninsula, Ambanizana village (Mahunka 1996c); Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) filifera
Mahunka, 1978

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) filifera Mahunka, 1978b: 337, figs 61–63.
Pergalumna filifera: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Australia, Mauritius, Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Frolov 2022a).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) frater Balogh, 1960

Pergalumna frater Balogh, 1960: 32, figs 54–58.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) frater: Ermilov & Starý 2020a: 73.
Pergalumna frater: Ermilov & Frolov 2022a: 444.

Distribution. Ethiopian region and Japan.

Locality in Madagascar. Montagne d'Ambre National Park (Ermilov & Starý 2020a).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) infinita
Mahunka, 2011

Pergalumna infinita Mahunka, 2011a: 180, figs 34–37.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) infinita: Subías 2016: 462.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Vohimana Reserve (Mahunka 2011a).

Pergalumna (Pergalumna) nasifera
Mahunka, 2011

Pergalumna nasifera Mahunka, 2011b: 63, figs 13a–c.
Pergalumna (Pergalumna) nasifera: Subías 2016: 463.

Distribution. Ethiopian region (Madagascar and Côte d'Ivoire).

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) (Mahunka 2011b).

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) Balogh, 1960

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) madagassica
Mahunka, 1996

Trichogalumna madagassica Mahunka, 1996c: 180, figs 34–37.

Trichogalumna madagassica: Mahunka 2002b: 15.

Trichogalumna madagassica: Balogh & Balogh 2002: 372, pl. 487, fig. 1.

Trichogalumna (Trichogalumna) madagassica: Subías 2008: 422.

Distribution. Endemic to Madagascar.

Locality in Madagascar. Andasibe (Perinet) Forest Reserve (Mahunka 1996c).

Excluded species from the Oribatid fauna of Madagascar

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) Balogh & Mahunka, 1979

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) puylaerti
Niedbala, 2001

Notophthiracarus puylaerti Niedbala, 2001: 53, figs 444–450.

Notophthiracarus puylaerti: Mahunka 2002b: 8.

Notophthiracarus puylaerti: Niedbala 2017: 131, fig. 88.

Phthiracarus (Archiphthiracarus) puylaerti: Subías 2022: 88.

Distribution. Ethiopian [Congo].

Remarks. This species is not a real member of the Malagasy mite fauna. It was originally described by Niedbala from Congo (Niedbala 2001), then most probably erroneously cited as a Madagascarian species by Mahunka (2002), referring to the original description (Niedbala 2001: 53). Later, making a new, partial revision of the country's ptyctimous mite fauna, Niedbala (2017) cited the species on the basis of Mahunka (2002).

DISCUSSION

So far, *ca.* 350 species of Oribatid mites have been recorded in Madagascar. [The currently known species and subspecies in the world are 11.435 (Subías 2022)]. Of the 63 Malagasy families and 154 genera, 311 species have been described from Madagascar (89%) of which 219 were described by Hungarian acarologists (70%): 144 by Mahunka, 18 by Mahunka & Mahunka-Papp, 56 by Balogh and 1 by Balogh & Mahunka. The next most fruitful authors are Niedbała (53), Ermilov (24) and Fernández (15) and their co-authors. From the 350 species 8 are cosmopolitan, 10 are semicosmopolitan, 10 species are restricted to the Ethiopian region, while 254 species (72%) are endemic to the island. The observed ratio of endemisms in a region is sometimes affected by artefacts such as lack of specialists/increased interest by a specialist or lack of collection activities/increased number of field trips. Madagascar has a long history of interest in its natural history, going back centuries (Andriamialisoa & Langrand 2003, Goodman & Benstead 2003). It is now well-known that the high ratio of endemism in the country can be derived from the island's biogeographical past (e.g. Vences *et al.* 2009). However, one can still feel surprised and astonished while directly discovering this biodiversity: “*The richness of this fauna is so high that it requires much more investigation than planned before*” (Mahunka 2011).

It is very sad to think of the many non-described species, non-published papers and monographs which could have been written by Sándor Mahunka and Luise Mahunka-Papp who deceased so prematurely. We are thankful for all those scientists who continue their work on the Oribatid fauna of Madagascar.

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